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Technical Guide on Scales and Indexes in National Surveys of Student Achievement (NSSA) Data

Developed under the project “Disparities in school achievement from a person and variable-oriented perspective: A prototype of a learning analytics tool NO-GAP”

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INTRODUCTION

In the context of digitalization and complex challenges facing contemporary educational systems and institutions, data collected in educational settings have a potential to become a central resource for educational organizations and other stakeholders. In relation to that, there is a growing need for systematic documentation and guidance on the possibilities of the existing educational datasets, collected and archived by public agencies, governmental or academic institutions.

The current Technical Guide explores some of the analytical possibilities provided by the National Surveys of Student Achievement (NSSA) data, collected in Lithuanian secondary schools during 2012-2016. The data is open access and can be downloaded from the website of the National Agency for Education¹, which also provides some technical documentation and empirical reports on the NSSAs. The aim of the current Guide is to explore the possibilities of traditional scaling approaches, and some alternatives, with the NSSA data in order to come up with a number of ready-made reliable indicators for the analyses of student achievement in the context of socio-economic disparities, which increasingly affect educational systems worldwide (Chmielewski, 2019). The indicators described in this Guide are oriented towards the analyses of achievement gaps related to socio-economic disparities among the Lithuanian students.

The focus on socio-economic disparities stems from the project that the Guide is an integral part of. The project “Disparities in school achievement from a person and variable-oriented perspective: A prototype of a learning analytics tool NO-GAP” (2020-2023) aims to develop a prototype of an analytical tool for monitoring and analyses of achievement gaps related to student socio-economic background. The task includes the development of a theoretical model, its operationalization and application on available educational data. In this respect, the NSSA data provide good possibilities for exploring the operationalization of the main indicators related to the aims of the project, but also for a broader analysis of educational achievement gaps in Lithuania. The NSSA data, based on nationally representative stratified two-stage nested samples, include standardized student achievement tests in math, reading, and other school subjects, as well as self-report questionnaires on student background, motivation, and learning environment at home and school.

The scales and indexes in this Guide, except for the indicators of student achievement, were developed specifically for the purposes of this project. The Guide is organized into sections based on the main indicators, which can be constructed or retrieved from the NSSA datasets. The first section addresses the indicators of student achievement and presents the analyses of their structure and measurement invariance in the NSSAs. The second section presents two different approaches for constructing the indicator of student socio-economic background. The next section presents several indicators of student motivational, emotional, and social functioning at school, which could be constructed by aggregating the NSSA items. The fourth section presents three aggregate indicators for assessing students’ perceptions of teacher behaviors at school. The final sections presents aggregate indicators for assessing support and

¹ <https://www.nsa.smm.lt/stebesenos-ir-vertinimo-departamentas/tyrimai/nacionaliniai-tyrimai/nacionaliniai-mokiniu-pasiekimu-tyrimai-nmpt/>

relationships in students' family. Each section presents a brief theoretical overview of the construct assessed, the operationalization of the construct in the NSSA data, extensive empirical information on descriptive statistics and some aspects of validity and reliability of the indicators. The analytical tools used to process the data include Mplus 8.5, several R packages, as well as SPSS. Specific tools were selected based on the availability of relevant statistical procedures, as well as user-friendly functionalities. The syntax files for all analyses reported in the Guide are available from the authors upon a reasonable request.

1. INSTRUMENTS AND STRATEGY FOR ASSESSING ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

1.1. Overview of NSSA assessment strategy and participants

National surveys of student achievements (NSSAs) are designed to provide country-level information about school students' achievement, which can be used to inform evidence-based decisions for improving educational policy and practices. While central to the NSSAs is an extensive assessment of achievements, these assessments are also accompanied by student and teacher questionnaires, which collect information about the social and educational context of learning. So far, four NSSAs were implemented: in 2012, 2014, 2015, and in 2016. These assessments are discussed further.

Each of the four NSSA was designed to provide a valid measurement of students' achievement in a particular domain, which is included in the national curricula. While the general approach to developing the achievement test was similar from one cycle (yearly study) to the next, each cycle had a unique goal that shaped the way the achievement test was designed. Throughout the four NSSA studies, six different domains of achievement were targeted. However, some of these were targeted consistently throughout the four studies, while others were targeted less consistently. Mathematics and reading skills domains were targeted consistently throughout the four years of study, writing skills were targeted three times, sciences and social studies – twice, and language structure – only once. More so, each of the NSSA studies were constructed with a focus on a few specific domains. That is, each NSSA study included major and minor assessment domains, which varied across the three cycles of NSSA. Major domains were those that were considered as most important at some particular cycle of NSSA and thus were studied, analyzed, and reported in official school achievement reports, more extensively. Assessments in major domains also involved more participants (school students). Minor domains were those that were considered less important and were not addressed in official reports. Minor assessments also involved fewer participants. However, minor domains did serve some other specific objectives. Table 1.1 summarized these domains.

<i>Achievement domain</i>	Year of the study			
	<i>2012</i>	<i>2014</i>	<i>2015</i>	<i>2016</i>
<i>Math</i>	Major	Major	Minor	Major
<i>Reading</i>	Major	Major	Minor	Major
<i>Writing</i>	Major	Not targeted	Minor	Minor
<i>Language structure</i>	Minor	Not targeted	Not targeted	Not targeted
<i>Social studies</i>	Not targeted	Minor	Major	Not targeted
<i>Sciences</i>	Not targeted	Minor	Major	Not targeted

The 2012 NSSA targeted achievement in mathematics (math), reading (in Lithuanian language), writing (in Lithuanian), and perception of language structure (short: language structure). Math, reading, and writing were major assessment domains. As such, more participants (school students) took part in these assessments. Language structure was considered as a minor domain, and consequently, fewer participants

took part in these assessments. Assessments of achievement in the language structure domain were also not addressed in the official achievement assessment reports.

The 2014 NSSA targeted achievement in math and reading (in Lithuanian), sciences, and social studies. Math and reading were major assessment domains. Consequently, the majority of participants took part in these assessments. Sciences and social studies were considered minor domains and were targeted primarily for experimental purposes. As such, fewer participants took part in these tests, and achievement in these domains was also not addressed in the official achievement assessment reports.

The 2015 NSSA targeted achievement in science (biology, chemistry, and physics), social studies (history, geography, and civic education), math, and reading (in Lithuanian). Science and social studies were major assessment domains. Consequently, the majority of participants took part in these assessments. Math and reading were considered minor domains. As such, fewer participants took part in these tests, and achievement in these domains was also not addressed in the official achievement assessment reports.

The 2016 NSSA targeted achievement in maths, reading (in Lithuanian), and writing (in Lithuanian). Math and reading were considered major domains, while writing was considered a minor domain.

Depending on the goals of each NSSA cycle, the assessments were conducted with fourth-, sixth-, and eighth-grade students. In particular, in 2012, 2014, and 2015, NSSA assessments were carried out with fourth- and eighth-grade students. While the 2016 cycle assessed only sixth-grade students. Considering that the NO-GAP study focuses mostly on middle school students, we did not involve or analyzed fourth-grade students. As such, Table 1.2 summarizes the number of students that took part in different NSSAs and the percentage that took part in domain-specific assessments, excluding the fourth-grade students for 2012, 2014, and 2015 datasets.

Table 1.2. The number of students that took part in different NSSAs and the percentage that took part in domain-specific assessments.				
<i>Achievement domain</i>	Year of the study			
	<i>2012 (8th grade)</i>	<i>2014 (8th grade)</i>	<i>2015 (8th grade)</i>	<i>2016 (6th grade)</i>
<i>Mathematics</i>	2988 (67%)	1702 (45%)	876 (25%)	2253 (83%)
<i>Reading</i>	2986 (67%)	1669 (44%)	873 (25%)	2250 (83%)
<i>Writing</i>	2984 (67%)	Not targeted	437 (13%)	906 (33%)
<i>Language systems</i>	2480 (55%)	Not targeted	Not targeted	Not targeted
<i>Social sciences</i>	Not targeted	1257 (33%)	2172 (62%)	Not targeted
<i>Natural sciences</i>	Not targeted	1256 (33%)	2606 (75%)	Not targeted
Total number of participants	4479	3763	3482	2710
Number of participating schools	160	148	147	115

1.1.1 Assessment design, the overlap between different assessment domains, and missing values

A major challenge for the extensive achievement assessment carried out in NSSA studies is a burden on schools and participants. In particular, the extensive assessment of achievement skills in multiple domains requires lengthy and time-consuming assessments. To reduce the burden on schools, teachers, and students, each NSSA study used a random allocation of domain-specific assessments. In particular, four NSSA uses a sampling approach that involves packaging different domain-specific assessments into a set of several student achievement booklets. The design of assessments and allocation of domain-specific assessment tasks into specific booklets varies from one cycle of NSSA to another. However, different booklets are always randomly distributed to students within each participating school.

One major implication of such an approach is that not all students who participate in the NSSA cycle are assessed in all of the achievement domains. For example, in 2012 (see Table X), 4479 8th grade students participated in the NSSA study. However, only 67% (n = 2988) were assessed in terms of mathematics achievement. As the allocation of different booklets is always random in each school, the percentage of students who are being evaluated on some specific domain is very similar in each school. Such a strategy ensures a rather accurate estimate of school-level achievement. However, it is not possible to very accurately estimate student-level achievement scores in each domain for each participant of the NSSA studies, due to missing values on an individual level for some of the participants and some achievement domains.

Analyzing such data presents some challenges. In particular, as it is possible to aggregate the individual achievement scores to get an accurate estimate of school achievement, studying contextual predictors of achievement on the school level is rather straightforward. However, studying predictors at school and individual level is more complex. Using the listwise deletion approach to deal with missing data will result in a substantial loss of statistical power, and in general, it is not a recommended strategy (Enders, 2011). Using FIML (Full information maximum likelihood) is a recommended option in such a situation, however, it may not be usable with some datasets. In particular, building a model with one outcome (e.g., math achievement) and not losing any information due to missing values is possible. However, building a model with several outcomes (achievement scores in multiple domains) may not be possible with some of the NSSA datasets, due to low covariance coverage for some of the domain-specific achievement scores.

The design of the 2012 NSSA study included and distributed booklets in a way that each domain-specific assessment was paired with another domain-specific assessment in at least 33% of cases. As such, it is possible to estimate a covariance between each domain of assessment (see Table 1.3). Thus, considering that booklets were distributed completely at random within each school, the 2012 dataset offers a possibility to analyze each domain-specific assessment separately and in concert, using FIML estimation. However, as language structure was a minor (experimental) achievement domain, the general recommendation is to analyze the scores on math, reading, and writing assessments.

Table 1.3.
Overlapping measurements in 2012 NSSA study, for 8th-grade students.

<i>Achievement</i>	Year of the study			
	<i>Math</i>	<i>Reading</i>	<i>Writing</i>	<i>Language structure</i>
<i>Mathematics</i>	2988	1495	1493	1998
<i>Reading</i>	33%	2986	1491	1475
<i>Writing</i>	33%	33%	2984	1487
<i>Language structure</i>	45%	33%	33%	2480

Note. The number on the diagonal indicates the number of participants that took a particular achievement test. Numbers above the diagonal indicate the number of participants that took a particular pair of tests. The number below the diagonal indicates covariance coverage (i.e., the percentage of participants that took a particular pair of tests).

The design of the 2014 NSSA study included and distributed booklets in a way that not all domain-specific assessment was paired with another. In particular, social studies and sciences were minor and experimental achievement domains and these were not paired with each other in a particular booklet. As such, it is not possible to estimate a covariance between the achievement scores in these domains (see Table 1.4). In this situation, it is generally recommended to investigate only math and reading scores that were the primary assessment domains. These two domains can also be analyzed in concert, using the FIML estimation. It is also possible to analyze social studies and sciences as outcomes of particular predictors, however, such analyses should be carried out separately for each of the two domains and not analyzing them in concert with other domain-specific achievement scores.

Table 1.4.
Overlapping measurements in 2014 NSSA study, for 8th-grade students.

<i>Achievement</i>	Year of the study			
	<i>Math</i>	<i>Reading</i>	<i>Social studies</i>	<i>Sciences</i>
<i>Mathematics</i>	1702	432	424	423
<i>Reading</i>	11%	1669	425	417
<i>Social studies</i>	11%	11%	1257	0
<i>Sciences</i>	11%	11%	0%	1256

Note. The number on the diagonal indicates the number of participants that took a particular achievement test. Numbers above the diagonal indicate the number of participants that took a particular pair of tests. The number below the diagonal indicates covariance coverage (i.e., the percentage of participants that took a particular pair of tests).

The design of the 2015 NSSA study targeted five domains, of which three were minor ones. As such, it also included and distributed booklets in a way that not all domain-specific assessment was paired with another. In particular, social studies and sciences were major domains, while the remaining three (math, reading, and writing) were minor ones and served other purposes. While the two primary domains were assessed in 50% of participants of the 2015 NSSA study, the remaining ones were not paired in many cases (see Table 1.5). As such, it is only possible to estimate a covariance between a few of the domains. Using this dataset, it is generally recommended to investigate only sciences and social studies as the outcomes of some predictors. These two domains can also be analyzed in concert, using the FIML estimation. However, for other domains, such analyses should be carried out using only a single domain as the outcome variable.

Table 1.5.
Overlapping measurements in 2015 NSSA study, for 8th-grade students.

<i>Achievement</i>	Year of the study				
	<i>Math</i>	<i>Reading</i>	<i>Writing</i>	<i>Social studies</i>	<i>Sciences</i>
<i>Mathematics</i>	876	441	0	435	0
<i>Reading</i>	13%	873	0	0	432
<i>Writing</i>	0%	0%	437	0	437
<i>Social studies</i>	50%	0%	0%	2172	1737
<i>Sciences</i>	0%	98%	100%	80%	2606

Note. The number on the diagonal indicates the number of participants that took a particular achievement test. Numbers above the diagonal indicate the number of participants that took a particular pair of tests. The number below the diagonal indicates covariance coverage (i.e., the percentage of participants that took a particular pair of tests).

Lastly, the design of the 2016 NSSA study targeted only three domains and distributed booklets in a way that each domain-specific assessment was paired with another domain-specific assessment in at least 33% of cases. As such, it is possible to estimate a covariance between each domain of assessment (see Table 1.6). Thus, considering that booklets were distributed completely at random within each school, the 2012 dataset offers a possibility to analyze each domain-specific assessment separately and in concert, using FIML estimation.

Table 1.6.
Overlapping measurements in 2016 NSSA study, for 6th-grade students.

<i>Achievement</i>	Year of the study		
	<i>Math</i>	<i>Reading</i>	<i>Writing</i>
<i>Mathematics</i>	2253	1798	453
<i>Reading</i>	66%	2250	452
<i>Writing</i>	17%	17%	906

Note. The number on the diagonal indicates the number of participants that took a particular achievement test. Numbers above the diagonal indicate the number of participants that took a particular pair of tests. The number below the diagonal indicates covariance coverage (i.e., the percentage of participants that took a particular pair of tests).

Differences between schools account from 12 to 28 % of variance in academic achievement. For two main subjects – Reading and Mathematics – it accounts for 14-20% and 16-27% of variance respectively for each subject (see ICC scores in table 1.7).

Table 1.7.
ICC (school) in 2012-2015 NSSA study, for 8th-grade students and 2016 NSSA study, for 6th-grade students.

<i>Achievement</i>	Year of the study			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
<i>Mathematics</i>	0.218	0.155	0.273	0.207
<i>Reading</i>	0.178	0.171	0.197	0.136
<i>Writing</i>	0.150		0.203	0.121
<i>Social studies</i>		0.203	0.173	
<i>Sciences</i>		0.276	0.118	
<i>Language structure</i>	0.193			

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in student academic achievement accounted by school-level differences.

1.1.2 Booklet design

A major consequence of NSSA's ambitious reporting goals is that many more questions are required for the assessment than can be answered by any student in the amount of testing time available. NSSA uses a matrix sampling approach that involves packaging the entire assessment pool of items (of each subject) into a set of several (it differs in different years and grades) student achievement booklets, with each student completing just one booklet. Each booklet has anchor items, providing a mechanism for linking together the student responses from the various booklets when data from all booklets are taken together. Booklets are distributed among students in participating classrooms randomly, seeking that the number of different booklets in each class is as equal as possible.

After the assessment has been administered and the data collected and processed, NSSA uses item response theory scaling methods to assemble a comprehensive picture of the achievement of the entire student population of a country from the combined responses of individual students to the booklets that they are assigned. This approach reduces to manageable proportions what otherwise would be an impossible student burden, albeit at the cost of some complexity in booklet assembly, data collection, and data analysis.

<i>Achievement</i>	Year of the study			
	<i>2012 (8th grade)</i>	<i>2014 (8th grade)</i>	<i>2015 (8th grade)</i>	<i>2016 (6th grade)</i>
<i>Mathematics</i>	6	4	2	5
<i>Reading</i>	6	4	2	5
<i>Writing</i>	5	0	1	2
<i>Language systems</i>	5	0	0	0
<i>Social sciences</i>	0	3	5	0
<i>Natural sciences</i>	0	3	6	0

1.2. Construction of mathematics achievement scores

1.2.1 The total score of mathematics achievement

The total score on mathematics achievement is constructed similarly across different cycles of the NSSA study. In particular, it is constructed using the two-parameter logistic model (2PLM; Birnbaum, 1968) for the binary item responses. The 2PLM is a generalization of the Rasch model (Rasch, 1960), which assumes that the probability of a correct response to an item depends only on the difference between the student's trait level and the difficulty of the item. The model accounts for the possibility that responses to different items do not have the same weight in relation to the latent trait. This approach is in line with those models used in international research, such as TIMSS, PISA, or PIRLS.

The total score on mathematics achievement is standardized so that the mean of the score in a particular study is 500 and the standard deviation is 100.

1.2.2 Content-specific mathematics achievement scores

The mathematics achievement test targets mathematics skills in five content domains. In particular, the test assesses skills in basic numbers and calculations, algebra, geometry, data and probability, and problem-solving. As such, the achievement test provides a possibility to estimate achievement in content-specific domains. The number of tasks included to assess each domain may vary from booklet to booklet and from one NSSA cycle to the next. However, the number of content domains is always equal across different NSSA cycles.

While tasks grouped into the five content-domains are different, the scores obtained from different math achievement domains show very high consistency. Table 1.9 shows Cronbach's alpha coefficients, i.e., estimates of consistency of the scores obtained from different math domains. These estimates indicate the very strong associations between scores in different domains for each of the booklets used, i.e., in every case alpha coefficient is higher than .85.

Year	Booklet/version of the test								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
2012	.92	.87			.86	.88	.91		.87
2014	.90		.92	.90		.92			
2015	.93	.92							
2016	.85	.87		.86	.85	.84			

The content domain-specific score on mathematics achievement is standardized so that the mean of the score in a particular study is 100 and the standard deviation is 15. The score is standardized for each booklet of the study, as such, this metric is identical across the studies and different booklets.

Table 1.10. Distribution of mathematics achievement scores

Considering that NSSA uses a matrix sampling approach, which involves packaging the entire assessment pool of items into a set of several achievement booklets, it is important to know if the total achievement scores from different booklets are comparable. To evaluate the comparability of different booklets, we tested for measurement invariance. In particular, we tested if the variance composition of overall mathematics achievement is similar across different booklets, i.e., we investigated if each of the content-domains contributes similarly to overall mathematics achievement. Considering that each booklet is standardized separately (the mean and variance of different booklets is identical), we only tested for metric invariance. That is we tested the assumption that each content-specific domain score is similarly related to the overall mathematics achievement.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) using Mplus 8.4 with Maximum Likelihood Robust (MLR) estimator was used to investigate measurement invariance. The choice of MLR estimator was based on the recommendations by Rhemtulla and colleagues (2012), which suggest the use of MLR estimator when scores are not completely normally distributed. Considering that the chi-square model fit statistic is sensitive to sample size (Kline, 2015), we used alternative indicators of model-data fit. In particular, we used The Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR), and the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), to assess model-data fit. RMSEA and SRMR lower than .08 indicated an acceptable level of model-data fit. RMSEA and SRMR lower than .05 indicated a good fit. CFI higher than .90 indicated acceptable fit and CFI higher than .95 indicated good fit (Brown, 2015). Measurement invariance was tested by employing a multiple group approach (booklet number indicated groups). That is, using the MG

approach we tested the fit of a single-dimension model for each booklet and then tested a second model, which imposed factor loading equality constraints across different booklets. The two models were compared using the “ Δ CFI” criterion, e.g., if newly added constraints (e.g., factor loading equality constraints) resulted in the decrease of CFI greater than .01, it indicated that a certain level of invariance (e.g., metric) does not hold (Cheung & Rensvold, 2002).

The results of measurement invariance analysis indicated that, across different booklets, content domain-specific mathematics achievement scores were similarly associated with the latent variable measuring overall math achievement. In particular, metric invariance, which was tested by adding equality factor loading constraints across different booklets did not result in a substantial decrease of model fit (Δ CFI did not exceed the -.01 threshold). In general, this result indicates that the scores obtained from different booklets can be used in a single analysis.

Table 1.11. Descriptive statistics of total and content-specific score on math achievement.

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	2988	1702	875	2257
<i>Total math test score (Mean = 500; SD = 100)</i>				
Min - Max	200 - 824	230 - 825	245 - 778	236 - 798
Skewness (S.E.)	-0,055 (0.045)	0,087 (0,59)	-0,132 (0,083)	0,158 (0,052)
Kurtosis (S.E.)	-0,374 (0.09)	-0,550 (0,119)	-0,571 (0,165)	-0,277 (0,103)
<i>Numbers and calculations (Mean = 100; SD = 15)</i>				
Min - Max	69 - 134	72 - 139	78 - 139	74 - 140
Skewness (S.E.)	0,045 (0.045)	0,087 (0,59)	0,426 (0,083)	0,262 (0,052)
Kurtosis (S.E.)	-0,857 (0.09)	-0,550 (0,119)	-0,831 (0,165)	-0,840 (0,103)
<i>Algebra (Mean = 100; SD = 15)</i>				
Min - Max	70 - 139	77 - 149	74 - 138	69 - 132
Skewness (S.E.)	0,292 (0.045)	0,637 (0,59)	0,357 (0,083)	0,082 (0,052)
Kurtosis (S.E.)	-0,751 (0.09)	-0,302 (0,119)	-0,721 (0,165)	-0,786 (0,103)
<i>Geometry and measurement (Mean = 100; SD = 15)</i>				
Min - Max	70 - 139	74-139	79 - 141	72 - 150
Skewness (S.E.)	0,321 (0.045)	0,354 (0,59)	0,430 (0,083)	0,540 (0,052)
Kurtosis (S.E.)	-0,831 (0.09)	-0,775 (0,119)	-0,789 (0,165)	-0,201 (0,103)
<i>Data and probability (Mean = 100; SD = 15)</i>				
Min - Max	53 - 127	66 - 134	68 - 129	63 - 137
Skewness (S.E.)	-0,300 (0.045)	0,005 (0,59)	0,148 (0,083)	-0,051(0,052)
Kurtosis (S.E.)	-0,568 (0.09)	-0,713 (0,119)	-0,914 (0,165)	-0,280 (0,103)
<i>Problem solving (Mean = 100; SD = 15)</i>				
Min - Max	58 - 157	74 - 150	72 - 143	74 - 144
Skewness (S.E.)	0,456 (0.045)	0,735 (0,59)	0,444 (0,083)	0,469 (0,052)
Kurtosis (S.E.)	0,145 (0.09)	-0,044 (0,119)	-0,274 (0,165)	-0,413 (0,103)

Table 1.12.

Results of measurement invariance analysis for different forms of mathematics achievement assessment

Model tested (model compared with)	Model fit statistics							Model comparison				
	χ^2	<i>df</i>	n_{par}	<i>p</i>	CFI	RMSEA [90% CI]	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	<i>P</i>	ΔCFI	$\Delta RMSEA$ A
<i>The year 2012 (6 different forms of the test)</i>												
Configural	55.237	30	90	.003	.997	.041 [.023 .058]	.013					
Weak (vs configural)	127.191	50	70	<.001	.990	.056 [.044 .068]	.110	73.677	20	<.001	-.007	.015
<i>The year 2014 (4 different forms of the test)</i>												
Configural	108.172	20	60	<.001	.991	.072 [.059 .086]	.014					
Weak (vs configural)	137.377	32	48	<.001	.990	.062 [.052 .073]	.061	25.503	12	.013	-.001	-.010
<i>The year 2015 (2 different forms of the test)</i>												
Configural	17.175	10	30	.071	.998	.040 [.000 .072]	.010					
Weak (vs configural)	24.976	14	26	.035	.996	.042 [.011 .069]	.067	7.907	4	.095	-.002	.002
<i>The year 2016 (5 different forms)</i>												
Configural												
Weak (vs configural)												

Note. CFI - Comparative Fit Index; RMSEA – Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; SRMR – Standardized Root Mean Square Residual; CI – Confidence Interval. n_{par} – number of free parameters in the model.

*** $p < .001$; ** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$.

1.3. Construction of reading achievement scores

1.3.1 The total score of readings achievement

The total score on reading achievement is constructed similarly to the mathematics test. In particular, it constructed using the two-parameter logistic model (2PLM; Birnbaum, 1968) for the binary item responses. The model accounts for the possibility that responses to different items do not have the same weight in relation to the latent trait. This approach is in line with those models used in international research, such as TIMSS, PISA, or PIRLS.

The total score on readings achievement is standardized so that the mean of the score in a particular study is 500 and the standard deviation is 100.

1.3.2 Content-specific reading achievement scores

The reading achievement test targets readings skills in four content domains. In particular, the test assesses skills in the retrieval of explicitly stated information, inference making, analysis, and interpretation and evaluation. As such, the achievement test provides a possibility to estimate achievement in content-specific domains. The number of tasks included to assess each domain may vary from booklet to booklet and from one NSSA cycle to the next. However, the number of content domains is always equal across different NSSA cycles.

While tasks grouped into the four content-domains are different, the scores obtained from different math achievement domains show very high consistency. Table 1.13 shows Cronbach's alpha coefficients, i.e., estimates of consistency of the scores obtained from different math domains. These estimates indicate the very strong associations between scores in different domains for each of the booklets used, i.e., in every case alpha coefficient is higher than .85.

Year	Booklet/version of the test								
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
2012	.85	.71	.82	.76	.82			.84	
2014	.85	.82					.82		.84
2015	.85		.86						
2016	.80	.83	.80	.78		.81			

The content domain-specific score on reading achievement is standardized so that the mean of the score in a particular study is 100 and the standard deviation is 15. The score is standardized for each booklet of the study, as such, this metric is identical across the studies and different booklets.

Considering that NSSA uses a matrix sampling approach, which involves packaging the entire assessment pool of items into a set of several achievement booklets, it is important to know if the total achievement scores from different booklets are comparable. To evaluate the comparability of different booklets, we tested for measurement invariance. In particular, we tested if the variance composition of overall reading achievement is similar across different booklets, i.e., we investigated if each of the content-domains contributes similarly to overall mathematics

achievement. Considering that each booklet is standardized separately (the mean and variance of different booklets is identical), we only tested for metric invariance. That is we tested the assumption that each content-specific domain score is similarly related to the overall mathematics achievement.

Table 1.14. Distribution of mathematics achievement scores

The results of measurement invariance analysis indicated that, across different booklets, content domain-specific reading achievement scores were similarly associated with the latent variable measuring overall math achievement. In particular, metric invariance, which was tested by adding equality factor loading constraints across different booklets did not result in a substantial decrease of model fit (ΔCFI did not exceed the .01 threshold). In general, this result indicates that the scores obtained from different booklets can be used in a single analysis.

Following data collection, student responses to the items in each assessment are aggregated and converted to the NSSA scale metrics at each grade level to provide an overall picture of the assessment results.

Table 1.15. Descriptive statistics of total and content-specific score on reading achievement.

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	2986	1669	873	2250
<i>Total reading test score (Mean = 500; SD = 100)</i>				
Min - Max	286 - 789	273 - 749	206 - 729	201 - 777
Skewness (S.E.)	-0,320 (0,045)	-0,317 (0,06)	-0,237 (0,083)	-0,203 (0,052)
Kurtosis (S.E.)	0,001 (0,09)	-0,075 (0,12)	-0,368 (0,105)	-0,186 (0,103)
<i>Retrieval of explicitly stated information (Mean = 100; SD = 15)</i>				
Min - Max	63 - 150	64 - 135	67 - 133	51 - 132
Skewness (S.E.)	-0,159 (0,045)	-0,081 (0,06)	-0,038 (0,083)	-0,269 (0,052)
Kurtosis (S.E.)	-0,477 (0,09)	-0,734 (0,12)	-0,717 (0,165)	-0,539(0,103)
<i>Making inferences (Mean = 100; SD = 15)</i>				
Min - Max	61 - 140	57 - 137	55 - 144	62 - 135
Skewness (S.E.)	-0,023 (0,045)	-0,18 (0,06)	-0,178 (0,083)	-0,117(0,052)
Kurtosis (S.E.)	-0,375 (0,09)	-0,503 (0,12)	-0,222 (0,165)	- 0,589(0,103)
<i>Analysis (Mean = 100; SD = 15)</i>				
Min - Max	56 - 150	67 - 129	59 - 140	64 - 145
Skewness (S.E.)	0,014 (0,045)	-0,403 (0,06)	0,144 (0,083)	0,055 (0,052)
Kurtosis (S.E.)	-0,593 (0,09)	-0,534 (0,12)	-0,615 (0,165)	-0,628 (0,103)
<i>Interpretation and evaluation (Mean = 100; SD = 15)</i>				
Min - Max	64 - 147	72 - 149	78 - 147	73 - 141
Skewness (S.E.)	-0,275 (0,045)	0,268 (0,06)	0,438 (0,083)	0,130 (0,052)
Kurtosis (S.E.)	-0,496 (0,09)	-0,609 (0,12)	-0,425 (0,165)	-0,807 (0,103)

Table 1.16.

Results of measurement invariance analysis for different forms of reading achievement assessment

Model tested (model compared with)	Model fit statistics							Model comparison				
	χ^2	<i>df</i>	n_{par}	<i>p</i>	CFI	RMSEA [90% CI]	SRMR	$\Delta\chi^2$	Δdf	<i>P</i>	ΔCFI	ΔRMSEA A
<i>The year 2012 (6 different forms of the test)</i>												
Configural	21.476	12	72	.044	.997	.040 [.007 .067]	.011					
Weak (vs configural)	58.353	27	57	<.001	.991	.048 [.031 .065]	.084	37.623	15	.001	-.006	.008
<i>The year 2014 (4 different forms of the test)</i>												
Configural	11.754	8	48	.163	.999	.024 [.000 .051]	.007					
Weak (vs configural)	93.484	17	39	<.001	.984	.073 [.059 .088]	.117	85.951	9	<.001	-.015	.049
<i>The year 2015 (2 different forms of the test)</i>												
Configural	23.383	4	24	<.001	.987	.105 [.067 .149]	.019					
Weak (vs configural)	33.439	7	21	<.001	.982	.093 [.063 .126]	.085	10.096	3	.018	-.005	-.012
<i>The year 2016 (5 different forms)</i>												
Configural												
Weak (vs configural)												

Note. CFI - Comparative Fit Index; RMSEA – Root Mean Square Error of Approximation; SRMR – Standardized Root Mean Square Residual; CI – Confidence Interval. n_{par} – number of free parameters in the model.

*** $p < .001$; ** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$.

2. ASSESSING STUDENT BACKGROUND: SOCIAL-ECONOMIC-CULTURAL INDEX

2.1 Theoretical conceptualization of the construct

Socio-economic status² is a relative position of a family or individual defined by their access to or control over valuable resources in a society, including wealth, power and status (Mueller & Parcel, 1981). Socio-economic status is related to such key aspects of human functioning as health, subjective well-being, academic achievement, or career (Diemer et al., 2013). The conceptualization and measurement of socio-economic status varies in scholarly literature and depends on the approach taken by the researchers. The American Psychological Association (APA, 2007) outlines three main approaches towards SES:

1. Materialist, which focuses on the role of material and structural factors and considers such quantifiable characteristics as income and wealth (Avvisati, 2020) or composite indicators constructed from a person's income, education, and occupation (APA, 2007), although the latter approach received substantial criticism (Sirin, 2005; Marks & Pokropek, 2019).
2. Gradient approach, which focuses on the effects of relative status and inequality. In this approach socio-economic status is constructed as a relative position, which reflects an individual's situation in relation to others. Traditional indicators – occupation (occupational prestige), education, income (wealth), as well as subjective judgements of one's social status – are used to construct gradient conceptualizations (APA, 2007; Avvisati, 2020).
3. Class-based model, which focuses on a person's position within the hierarchical capitalist economy (possession of property, position in labour market and access to other resources). It is usually conceptualized and measured as an (ordered) categorical construct wherein classes are defined as reflecting certain types of economic activity and status (APA, 2007; Avvisati, 2020).

Some conceptualizations of SES stress that not only material resources (i.e., financial capital) determine the actual social status of a person or a family in a society, but also cultural and social resources (i.e., social, cultural or human capital) (Tramonte & Willms, 2010). For example, in educational research, including PISA surveys, an index of social-economic-cultural (SEC) status is used, which is defined as “a measure of students' access to family resources (financial capital, social capital, cultural capital and human capital) which determine the social position of the student's family/household” (Avvisati, 2020, p. 3). Some studies demonstrate that material and cultural aspects have different implications for an individual outcomes, such as educational attainment (e.g., Yang, 2003).

Measurement of SES among school-aged children and adolescents often relies on traditional indicators of parental education, occupation, and/ or income (Diemer et al., 2013). It has been shown, however, that the use of these traditional indicators for SEC

² In this text we use concepts of socio-economic status, social-economic-cultural status, social status and social class interchangeably, except, in cases where the distinction is explicitly mentioned and described.

assessment among children and adolescents has a number of limitations (Currie et al., 2008; Sirin, 2005), including large proportions of missing data and a lack of reliability (Aaro et al., 2009; Currie et al., 2008). An alternative way to assess SEC among children and adolescents is using a composite measure consisting of multiple items specifying home possessions of the child's family (Currie et al., 2008; OECD, 2014; Sirin, 2005; Yang, 2003), including items indicating family wealth (e.g., a number of cars owned by a family), cultural possessions (e.g., musical instruments at home), and home educational resources (e.g., availability of a computer for educational purposes) (OECD, 2017). The advantage of such measures are high levels of response in child and adolescent samples (Currie et al., 1997). Large cross-national studies on adolescent educational achievement and health include similar measures of SEC background (e.g., Currie et al., 2008; OECD, 2014).

2.2 Operationalization of the construct in NSSA data

Multiple items measuring different aspects of SEC were included into NSSA data: related to both more traditional way of SES measurement (parental education, parental employment and supervisory status, pocket-money per week, eligibility for free meals at school, consultation by a private tutor) as well as related to measurement method based on home possessions of the child's family (number of books at home, possession of own books and encyclopaedia at home, possession of musical instruments and art-related objects, possession of 3+ computers and a dishwasher).

For the construction of the index items measuring parental education, parental employment and supervisory status were dropped as they either have low variability or have a lot of missing cases (see Table 2.2.) However, these items were employed for the assessment of external validity of the scales. Item measuring students' pocket-money per week was dropped due to low association with other items as revealed by the confirmatory factor analysis (see Section on validity of the scales). However, it was also used for the assessment of external validity of the resultant indexes.

The final set of items that were used for constructing SEC indexes included:

1. **Number of books at home** (measured on a 5-point ordinal scale, see Table 2.1).
2. **Possession of 6 types of things**: own books, encyclopaedia, musical instrument, works of art/albums, three or more computers and dishwasher at home (measured on a binary scale (yes/no), see Table 2.1).
3. **Eligibility for free meals at school** (measured on a binary scale (yes/no), see Table 2.1).
4. **Frequency of consultation by a private tutor** (measured on a binary scale (never or almost never/sometimes vs. at least once a month), see Table 2.1).

Notably, the answer scale of the last question was different between survey conducted in 2012 and other years. However, this fact did not seem to have a substantial effect on the index construction (see Section on validity of the scales).

We used two procedures to construct the SEC index: confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and multiple correspondence analysis (MCA). We called labelled the index based on CFA procedure SEC_I and the index based on MCA approach - SEC_D1. The following indexes and the procedures used to obtain them are presented below.

2.2.1 Development of SEC index based on CFA procedure

CFA is a common method for scale construction when items measuring a construct or its dimensions are well-known in advance and have good theoretical background. Importantly, this technique can accommodate both continuous and categorical variables, which was important in our case as all of our items were measured on either nominal or ordinal scale. However, it is less well suited for dimensional, exploratory analysis. Notwithstanding, we used it for constructing our unidimensional SEC_I index, as we expected unidimensional nature of the SEC construct to emerge. In particular, we employed weighted least squares mean and variance adjusted (WLSMV) estimation implemented in the Mplus 8.6 software in order to account for categorical (in most cases binary) nature of the data and non-normality of the not-binary item³. All items were declared as categorical and Delta parametrization used with probit link function. In order to improve the fit of the estimated model two correlated errors were included into the model: 1) At home: musical instruments vs. At home: works of art/albums; 2) At home: three or more computers vs. At home: dishwasher. The analysis was performed on all the groups (years) separately, as measurement invariance (metric, in particular) did not hold for the joint dataset (see Section on validity of the scales). Factor scores resulting from the performed CFAs were saved and comprise the estimates of the index. Higher scores indicate higher SEC.

The structure of SEC index was analysed for each year and group of students separately, and the results of CFA for a single-factor model supported it (see Tables 2.3a – 2.3d). The overall fit to the data was observed at all NSSA assessment times, however, not all indicators proved equally stable and robust across different datasets. The highest and most robust loadings were observed for the following indicators: free meals at school, number of books, own books, encyclopaedia, musical instruments and works of art at home. Lower and less stable/robust loadings were observed for the rest of the indicators: three or more computers and a dishwasher at home and access to a private tutor. The latter had a particularly weak loading in the data collected from the 6th grade students. Despite some variations in the strength of the indicators for the single-factor SEC indicator, the same structure was retained across different datasets.

2.2.2 Development of SEC index based on MCA approach

MCA is a statistical method the dimensional analysis of categorical data consisting of more than two variables (Greenacre, 2017). It is a descriptive method allowing visual portrayal of interrelations of categories of multiple categorical variables. MCA has several implementations (based on indicator matrix, based on the Burt table (with or without adjustment of inertias), joint correspondence analysis, see Greenacre, 2017), and indicator matrix approach is the most commonly used⁴. This approach is based on recoding of original categorical data into indicator matrix where each category has its own column and the values are 1 (if a case belongs to that category) and 0 (if a case does not belong to that category). Then MCA is a statistical technique for visualising data of this “two-way table” by calculating coordinates representing both its rows and

³ Also, this estimation method treats missing values on a case by case basis, which allows to eliminate missing values in the scores.

⁴ It is important to note that the solutions resulting from all the different methods employed are almost identical.

columns⁵. These coordinates are analogous to factor loadings in a principal components analysis, factor analysis or multidimensional scaling except that they partition the Chi-square value (usually called inertia) instead of the total variance.

Although dimensions onto which coordinates are transferred invite for interpretation, their interpretation in MCA is different from that in factor analysis (Greenacre, 2017). This is mostly due to the fact that categories of categorical variables (columns) and cases (rows) are analysed separately, but then plotted together using a biplot, where positions of categories and cases might be quite arbitrary⁶. Since the two spaces (separately constructed for categories of categorical variables (columns) and cases (rows)) are portrayed on the plot⁷, singular interpretation (or “naming”) of axes (dimensions) is difficult. Usually, in MCA one first proceeds by looking at the “solution of categories” and trying to identify which categories are opposed one to the other on the first and the second dimensions⁸ for each variable separately and then trying to identify if there is any structure to the distribution of points. Importantly, distances between the points of categories represent Chi-square (and not Euclidean) differences and, therefore, are quite abstract quantities.

Spatial locations of categories of variables provide visual picture of the pattern of relationship between the variables analysed. For categories of separate variables, angle between the origin and the two points (categories) is most important. If the angle is small (close to 0°), the two categories are positively related. If the angle is 90°, the two categories are not related at all. And if angle is 180° (they are opposite each other), the two categories are negatively related. Further, the more distant the points are from the origin, the more distinctive they are from the average profile. Therefore, points close to the origin of the plot are not very interesting for the interpretation of MCA results. Finally, it is important to note that all the results of MCA are relative, that is, they have to be interpreted taking into consideration all the categories of variables not just few selected ones.

First, we estimated the optimal number of dimensions of MCA solution for each group with the function *estim_ncpMCA()* included into the *missMDA* package of the *R* software environment for statistical computing and graphics (Josse & Husson, 2016). We employed *Kfold* (cross-validation) algorithm with *pNA* parameter (indicating the percentage of missing values inserted and predicted with MCA using *nep.min=0* to *nep.max=5* dimensions) = 0.05, and *nbsim* parameter (the number of times the process is repeated) = 100. The resulting analysis showed that 2-dimensional solution for all the groups (years) produced the lowest value of the mean square error of prediction (MSEP), criterion used to evaluate the optimal dimensionality of MCA solutions (Josse & Husson, 2016) (Table 2.4).

⁵ For comprehensive introductions into MCA see Le Roux and Rouanet (2004), Le Roux and Rouanet (2009), Greenacre (2017), Husson, Le and Pagès (2017).

⁶ Coordinate scores are variously transformed in order to allow for different types of interpretation.

⁷ Simultaneous portrayal is only possible because the origins of the two spaces (for categories of categorical variables and cases) coincide and the variation (both total and for each separate dimension) is the same.

⁸ Or any other combination of dimensions, if more than two of them are retained in the final solution.

The second step consisted of performing the (regularized⁹) iterative MCA algorithm with the number of dimensions selected in the previous step (2 in our case), using the function *imputeMCA()* from the R package *missMDA* in order to impute missing values for subsequent MCA analysis. Finally, in the third step (indicator matrix) MCA was performed on the imputed dataset and standard coordinates of the two dimensions of the MCA solutions were saved. The standard coordinates (similar in interpretation to factor scores of the CFA solution) of the first of these dimensions constitutes values of the SEC_D1 index. In order to simplify interpretation, values of the index were reversed, so that higher index scores indicate higher SEC. Standard coordinates of the second dimension were also saved in order to perform further analysis of their substantive meaning.

The graphical representations of MCA solutions in Fig. 2.1a – 2.1d show that the categories of separate variables are dispersed along the first dimension (horizontal) following the logic of higher vs. lower SEC: on the positive side of the first dimension we find categories indicating lack of home possessions, eligibility for free meals at school and no tutoring. The “opposite” categories are clustered on the negative side of the first dimension.

Relative contributions are usually calculated for each dimension in order to provide quantitative estimates of the contribution of each category (or case) to the inertia (total variance) of the dimension (Husson, Le & Pagès, 2017: 82-83)¹⁰. The higher the value of the relative contribution, the more the particular category contributes to the construction (identification) of the dimension under consideration¹¹. If we look at the relative contributions of categories to the first dimension we see that the three categories of low SEC (not having an encyclopedia at home, having only 1-10 books at home, in general, and being eligible for free meals at school) score highest, meaning that these three separate categories are most important for identifying (constructing) the first dimension. A more usual statistics eta-squared also shows that the same three variables (not separate categories) and having a musical instrument at home best explain the variance of the first dimension (Tables 2.5a – 2.5d).

The graphical representations of MCA solutions in Fig. 2.1a – 2.1d show that the categories of separate variables are also dispersed along the second dimension (vertical) following the logic of higher versus lower typicality of answers: the scores towards the higher end of this dimension indicate increasingly less typical, more contradictory patterns of available resources in the family, while the scores towards the lower end indicate very similar, consistent answers on items assessing SEC background of the students. Since this dimension does not provide a direct measure of SEC, the second dimension (SEC_D2) is not given an in-depth consideration in this report. However, it is notable that the results of MCA suggest that this second

⁹ The regularized version is more appropriate in order to avoid overfitting issues (Josse & Husson, 2016).

¹⁰ Their substantive interpretation is similar to factor loadings in EFA or CFA.

¹¹ There are additional measures (cosine-squared for the angle separating vectors of a category (case) and a dimension as well as v.test statistics, see Greenacre, 2017; Husson, Le & Pagès, 2017) that help to evaluate how well categories are represented by a dimension under consideration or how different are values of dimension coordinate estimates for a particular category compared to all the values (substantively similar to communalities in EFA). However, estimates of relative contributions are better suited for interpretation of dimensions.

dimension (SEC_D2) should be controlled for in the models that assess the links between SEC_D1 and other variables in order to account for the “noise”, or more precisely, (un)typicality of answers, when assessing SEC among students. Controlling for SEC_D2 should help to assess the true links between SEC_D1 (i.e., the students’ social-economic-cultural status) and other variables.

Finally, in order to have a categorical variable for the assessment of student achievement social inequalities we divided SEC_D1 values into quintiles using *quantile()* function available in the *R* software. For calculating quintiles we used algorithm called “Type 8” and recommended by Hyndman and Fan (1996), which calculates continuous sample quantiles so that the resulting quantile estimates are approximately median-unbiased regardless of the distribution of values of the transformed variable.

2.3 Descriptive statistics

Descriptives for the three interval-level SEC indexes are presented in Tables 2.6a and 2.6b, and histograms in Table 2.8. The scores for the simple aggregate index SEC_I are distributed relatively symmetrically around the mean. The scores are slightly negatively skewed in 2015 and 2016 datasets, indicating there are slightly more of those who have a relatively higher number of belongings compared to those who have a relatively low number of belongings.

The scores for the first dimension SEC_D1 of the two-dimensional index are distributed relatively symmetrically around the mean in 2012 dataset, however, the distribution becomes increasingly negatively skewed in more recent datasets. This indicates that more recently the participants tend to increasingly have access to the material, cultural and educational family resources listed in the questionnaire – the share of those who have relatively few resources is reducing, while the share of those who have relatively many resources is increasing. Also, those towards the higher end of the dimension become increasingly similar in their possession of resources – the maximum value becomes closer towards the mean in later assessments. This reveals a reducing potential of the items included in the questionnaire to distinguish between social-economic-cultural situation of the participants, particularly, on the higher end of the continuum.

The scores for the second dimension SEC_D2 of the two-dimensional index have a special interpretation considering the construct assessed by this dimension. The scores towards the right end of the dimension indicate increasingly less typical, more contradictory patterns of available resources in the family, while the scores towards the left end indicate very similar, consistent answers. Thus, the overall positive skew of SEC_D2 distribution suggests that most of the participants provide rather consistent and similar answers about the resources available at home. However, there is a part of the sample who answer in a more contradictory fashion regarding the items available in the family compared to the rest of the participants. This tendency is slightly stronger in earlier datasets.

Descriptives for the categorical SEC_C index are presented in Table 2.6c. This index can be used for dividing the sample into five equal subgroups (quintiles), based on the

social-economic-cultural context. The first, third and fifth quintiles have been used previously as proxies for low, medium, and high socio-economic classes with international student achievement data (Zabulionis, 2020). Consistently with observations from descriptives on SEC_D1, the range of values for the highest quintile is decreasing over time, while the range of values for the lowest quintile is increasing. It suggests that those with the most favorable socio-economic situation are becoming slightly more similar amongst themselves, while those with the least favorable socio-economic situation are becoming slightly more differentiated amongst themselves.

As suggested by intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) estimates, in case of SEC_I, SEC_D1 and the categorical SEC_C indexes the differences between schools account for 17,9% to 23,7% of variance. In case of SEC_D2 the differences between schools are smaller – they account for 3,9% to 6,5 % of variance (see ICC scores in Tables 2.6 a, b, c).

2.4 Scale validity in NSSA data

We explored the validity and reliability aspects of SEC_I and SEC_D1 indexes separately, since different analytical approaches were used in their construction.

2.4.1 Validity of SEC_I index

We checked measurement invariance of the SEC index across different years and groups of students investigated in the NSSA. We were able to confirm configural and metric invariance of the index (fit statistics for a CFA model¹² with loadings fixed across groups (i.e., year of assessment): $X^2 = 578.760$ (df=124, $p < 0.001$; CFI = 0.963; RMSEA = 0.032 (90% CI: 0.029-0.035, $p=1$; SRMR = 0.050). However, we were able to confirm only partial scalar invariance of the SEC index. This result indicates that scale means are different across years and groups of students investigated in the NSSA. Since the groups are defined as temporal objects, the outcome is rather expected. However, it also means that the groups should not be analysed together, at least, if temporal (group) dimension is not included into the model explicitly.

We also assessed criterion validity of the SEC_I index constructed by means of CFA (Table 2.7a). As it was mentioned, for the final construction of the index items measuring parental education, parental employment status and item measuring students' pocket-money per week were not used, but we used them for the assessment of external validity of the scales. The findings indicated from week to moderate positive correlations between these items and SEC_I index. Moderate correlations (.35-.43) were observed between SEC_I index and parents' education and specific parental employment (job in the field of management) (.21-.26). Correlation between SEC_I index and students' pocket-money and between SEC_I index and parental employment status (item assessed on a 3 point scale: 3: *work a paid full time job*, 2: *work part-time*

¹² CFA performed with Mplus 8.6: weighted least squares mean and variance adjusted (WLSMV) estimation was used in order to account for categorical (binary) nature of the data and non-normality of the not-binary item. All items declared as categorical, parametrization – Theta, link function – Probit. Inter-item correlations included into the model: At home: Musical instruments vs. At home: Works of art; At home: Three or more computers vs. At home: Dishwasher.

paid job, 1: do not work) is weak (.14-.19 and .11-.18 respectively). The patterns in different years were the same.

2.4.2 Validity of SEC_D1 index

In order to evaluate how reliable (internally consistent) are dimensions of the MCA solution we calculated estimates of internal consistency¹³ for the solution including all the variables and solutions when one variable is removed. The results of the analysis showed that for all the samples (groups and years) the estimates of internal consistency for the solution including all the variables (ranging from 0.54 to 0.60) are higher than those when any of the variables are removed.

We also assessed criterion validity of the SEC_D1 index constructed by means of MCA (Table 2.7b). The findings indicated from weak to moderate positive correlations between validation items and SEC_D1 index. Moderate correlations (.40-.44) were observed between SEC_D1 index and parents' education and specific parental employment (job in the field of management) (.23-.30). Correlation between SEC_D1 index and students' pocket-money and between SEC_D1 index and parental employment status (item assessed on a 3 point scale: 3: *work a paid full time job*, 2: *work part-time paid job*, 1: *do not work*) is weak (.16-.22 and .11-.19 respectively). The patterns in different years were the same.

¹³ For the calculation of the estimates of internal consistency we used formula and the logic presented in Greenacre (2017: 159-160). It is based on the values of principal inertias (of the indicator matrix based MCA) and is monotonically related to Cronbach's alpha measure of reliability (internal consistency). In general, the higher the principal inertia (explained variance), the higher the reliability (internal consistency).

Table 2.1. SEC Index: Structure and syntax

Items			
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
<p>B5/How many books are there at Your home, approximately? Response scale: <i>1 1-10 books</i> <i>2 11-25 books</i> <i>3 26-100 books</i> <i>4 101-200 books</i> <i>5 More than 200 books</i></p>	<p>B5/How many books are there at Your home, approximately? Response scale: <i>1 1-10 books</i> <i>2 11-25 books</i> <i>3 26-100 books</i> <i>4 101-200 books</i> <i>5 More than 200 books</i></p>	<p>B5/How many books are there at Your home, approximately? Response scale: <i>1 1-10 books</i> <i>2 11-25 books</i> <i>3 26-100 books</i> <i>4 101-200 books</i> <i>5 More than 200 books</i></p>	<p>B4/How many books are there at Your home, approximately? Response scale: <i>1 1-10 books</i> <i>2 11-25 books</i> <i>3 26-100 books</i> <i>4 101-200 books</i> <i>5 More than 200 books</i></p>
Intro: Do you have at your home:			
<p>B6a/Your own books (do not include textbooks) B6b/ an encyclopedia B6g/ a musical instrument (e.g., piano, guitar, etc.) B6h/ works of art, artistic photography albums B6i/ a total number of computers is three or more B6j/ a dishwasher Response scale: <i>1 Yes</i> <i>2 No</i></p>	<p>B6a/Your own books (do not include textbooks) B6b/ an encyclopedia B6g/ a musical instrument (e.g., piano, guitar, etc.) B6h/ works of art, artistic photography albums B6i/ a total number of computers is three or more B6j/ a dishwasher Response scale: <i>1 Yes</i> <i>2 No</i></p>	<p>B6a/Your own books (do not include textbooks) B6b/ an encyclopedia B6h/ a musical instrument (e.g., piano, guitar, etc.) B6i/ works of art, artistic photography albums B6j/ a total number of computers is three or more B6k/ a dishwasher Response scale: <i>1 Yes</i> <i>2 No</i></p>	<p>B5a/Your own books (do not include textbooks) B5b/ an encyclopedia B5h/ a musical instrument (e.g., piano, guitar, etc.) B5i/ works of art, artistic photography albums B5j/ a total number of computers is three or more B5k/ a dishwasher Response scale: <i>1 Yes</i> <i>2 No</i></p>
<p>B8/ Do you receive free meals at school: Response scale:</p>	<p>B8/ Do you receive free meals at school: Response scale:</p>	<p>B8/ Do you receive free meals at school: Response scale:</p>	<p>B7/ Do you receive free meals at school: Response scale:</p>

Items			
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
<i>1 Yes</i> <i>2 No</i>	<i>1 Yes</i> <i>2 No</i>	<i>1 Yes</i> <i>2 No</i>	<i>1 Yes</i> <i>2 No</i>
Intro: Who helps you with extra studying besides regular class hours:			
B20a/ A tutor (paid teacher, who helps to study) or several tutors Response scale: <i>1 Never</i> <i>2 At least sometimes</i>	B20a/ A tutor (paid teacher, who helps to study) or several tutors Response scale: <i>1 Never or almost never</i> <i>2 At least 1 time per month</i>	B17a/ A tutor (paid teacher, who helps to study) or several tutors Response scale: <i>1 Never or almost never</i> <i>2 At least 1 time per month</i>	B17a/ A tutor (paid teacher, who helps to study) or several tutors Response scale: <i>1 Never or almost never</i> <i>2 At least 1 time per month</i>
Missings:		98, 99	
Indexes			
Aggregate index			
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
One-dimensional index: SEC_I = factors scores from CFA ¹⁴ on 9 items: B5 + B6a + B6b + B6g + B6h + B6i + B6j + B8 + B20a Before CFA: 1 Values of items B6 were recoded into 0-No and 1-Yes. 2 Values of item B8 were recoded into 0-Yes and 1-	One-dimensional index: SEC_I = factors scores from CFA on 9 items: B5 + B6a + B6b + B6g + B6h + B6i + B6j + B8 + B20a Before CFA: 1 Values of items B6 were recoded into 0-No and 1-Yes. 2 Values of item B8 were recoded into 0-Yes and 1-	One-dimensional index: SEC_I = factors scores from CFA on 9 items: B5 + B6a + B6b + B6h + B6i + B6j + B6k + B8 + B17a Before CFA: 1 Values of items B6 were recoded into 0-No and 1-Yes. 2 Values of item B8 were recoded into 0-Yes and 1-	One-dimensional index: SEC_I = factors scores from CFA on 9 items: B4 + B5a + B5b + B5h + B5i + B5j + B5k + B7 + B17a Before CFA: 1 Values of items B5 were recoded into 0-No and 1-Yes. 2 Values of item B7 were recoded into 0-Yes and 1-

¹⁴ Estimation technique is described on page 5.

Items			
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
No. 3 Values of item B20a were recoded into 0-Never and 1-At least sometimes.	No. 3 Values of item B20a were recoded into 0-Never or almost never and 1-At least 1 time per month.	No. 3 Values of item B17a were recoded into 0-Never or almost never and 1-At least 1 time per month.	No. 3 Values of item B17a were recoded into 0-Never or almost never and 1-At least 1 time per month.
Two-dimensional index: SEC_D1 = reversed standard coordinates of Dim1 of indicator matrix MCA on 9 items: B5 + B6a + B6b + B6g + B6h + B6i + B6j + B8 + B20a	Two-dimensional index: SEC_D1 = reversed standard coordinates of Dim1 of indicator matrix MCA on 9 items: B5 + B6a + B6b + B6g + B6h + B6i + B6j + B8 + B20a	Two-dimensional index: SEC_D1 = reversed standard coordinates of Dim1 of indicator matrix MCA on 9 items: B5 + B6a + B6b + B6h + B6i + B6j + B6k + B8 + B17a	Two-dimensional index: SEC_D1 = reversed standard coordinates of Dim1 of indicator matrix MCA on 9 items: B4 + B5a + B5b + B5h + B5i + B5j + B5k + B7 + B17a
Two-dimensional index: SEC_D2 = standard coordinates of Dim2 of indicator matrix MCA on 9 items: B5 + B6a + B6b + B6g + B6h + B6i + B6j + B8 + B20a	Two-dimensional index: SEC_D2 = standard coordinates of Dim2 of indicator matrix MCA on 9 items: B5 + B6a + B6b + B6g + B6h + B6i + B6j + B8 + B20a	Two-dimensional index: SEC_D2 = standard coordinates of Dim2 of indicator matrix MCA on 9 items: B5 + B6a + B6b + B6h + B6i + B6j + B6k + B8 + B17a	Two-dimensional index: SEC_D2 = standard coordinates of Dim2 of indicator matrix MCA on 9 items: B4 + B5a + B5b + B5h + B5i + B5j + B5k + B7 + B17a
Categorical index: SEC_C = quintiles constructed from SEC_D1 using R function <i>quantile()</i> (calculation algorithm = “Type 8”)	Categorical index: SEC_C = quintiles constructed from SEC_D1 using R function <i>quantile()</i> (calculation algorithm = “Type 8”)	Categorical index: SEC_C = quintiles constructed from SEC_D1 using R function <i>quantile()</i> (calculation algorithm = “Type 8”)	Categorical index: SEC_C = quintiles constructed from SEC_D1 using R function <i>quantile()</i> (calculation algorithm = “Type 8”)

Table 2.2. Items measuring parental education, parental employment and supervisory status, that were dropped and not included in the SEC index.

	2012		2014		2015		2016	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
What is your mother occupation?								
Working a paid full time job	2485	55,5	2111	56,1	1901	54,6	1349	49,8
Working a paid part- time job	1060	23,7	850	22,6	897	25,8	742	27,4
Does not work	585	13,1	511	13,6	391	11,2	297	11,0
I do not know	298	6,7	246	6,5	212	6,1	262	9,7
Answer is not administered (missing)	1	,0	7	,2	5	,1	11	,4
No answer (missing)	50	1,1	38	1,0	76	2,2	49	1,8
Total	4479	100,0	3763	100,0	3482	100,0	2710	100,0
What is your father occupation?								
Working a paid full time job	2768	61,8	2335	62,1	2171	62,3	1598	59,0
Working a paid part- time job	686	15,3	584	15,5	599	17,2	525	19,4
Does not work	309	6,9	244	6,5	161	4,6	127	4,7
I do not know	579	12,9	474	12,6	417	12,0	368	13,6
Answer is not administered (missing)	2	,0	6	,2	9	,3	8	,3
No answer (missing)	135	3,0	120	3,2	125	3,6	84	3,1
Total	4479	100,0	3763	100,0	3482	100,0	2710	100,0
Is your mother currently working abroad?								
Yes	142	3,2	137	3,6	115	3,3	90	3,3
No	4098	91,5	3460	91,9	3134	90,0	2462	90,8
Answer is not administered (missing)			3	,1	1	,0	1	,0
No answer (missing)	239	5,3	163	4,3	232	6,7	157	5,8
Total	4479	100,0	3763	100,0	3482	100,0	2710	100,0
Is your father currently working abroad?								
Yes	596	13,3	484	12,9	477	13,7	463	17,1
No	3731	83,3	3126	83,1	2876	82,6	2165	79,9
Answer is not administered (missing)	2	,0	4	,1			2	,1
No answer (missing)	150	3,3	149	4,0	129	3,7	80	3,0
Total	4479	100,0	3763	100,0	3482	100,0	2710	100,0
What is your mother/guardian education?								
University/higher education	1754	39,2	1440	38,3	1447	41,6	1057	39,0
Post Secondary (not higher) education	773	17,3	580	15,4	487	14,0	292	10,8
Vocational education	589	13,2	625	16,6	492	14,1	295	10,9
Secondary education	363	8,1	276	7,3	226	6,5	151	5,6
Basic education	62	1,4	87	2,3	72	2,1	74	2,7
No basic education	5	,1	9	,2	6	,2	6	,2
I do not know	836	18,7	653	17,4	621	17,8	715	26,4
Answer is not administered (missing)	51	1,1	56	1,5	55	1,6	93	3,4
No answer (missing)	46	1,0	37	1,0	76	2,2	27	1,0
Total	4479	100,0	3763	100,0	3482	100,0	2710	100,0
What is your father/guardian education?								
University/higher education	1114	24,9	825	21,9	907	26,0	706	26,1
Post Secondary (not higher) education	962	21,5	804	21,4	666	19,1	385	14,2
Vocational education	671	15,0	714	19,0	590	16,9	316	11,7
Secondary education	307	6,9	246	6,5	217	6,2	126	4,6
Basic education	77	1,7	82	2,2	79	2,3	99	3,7
No basic education	15	,3	8	,2	12	,3	8	,3
I do not know	1171	26,1	931	24,7	867	24,9	938	34,6
Answer is not administered (missing)	45	1,0	48	1,3	42	1,2	82	3,0

	2012		2014		2015		2016	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
No answer (missing)	117	2,6	105	2,8	102	2,9	50	1,8
Total	4479	100,0	3763	100,0	3482	100,0	2710	100,0

Table 2.3a. Weighted least squares mean and variance adjusted estimates and fit statistics for single-factor models of the social-economic-cultural index (SEC_I) items: 8th grade, 2012.

Items	8 th grade, 2012					
	Estimate	S.E.	p-value	Resid. variance	Std. estimate	R ²
Number of books at home	1.000	--	--	0.556	0.666	0.444
At home: Own books	0.696	0.049	0.000	0.785	0.463	0.215
At home: Encyclopedia	1.120	0.046	0.000	0.444	0.746	0.556
At home: Musical instruments	0.697	0.038	0.000	0.785	0.464	0.215
At home: Works of art	0.502	0.038	0.000	0.888	0.334	0.112
At home: Three or more computers	0.472	0.039	0.000	0.901	0.314	0.099
At home: Dishwasher	0.464	0.039	0.000	0.904	0.309	0.096
Free meal at school	0.706	0.039	0.000	0.779	0.470	0.221
Private tutor	0.476	0.040	0.000	0.899	0.317	0.101
Model characteristics						
X²			221.131 (df=25, p<0.001)			
Comparative Fit Index			0.946			
Tucker-Lewis Index			0.922			
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation			0.042 (90% CI: 0.037-0.047, p (probability RMSEA <= .05) = 0.996			
Standardized Root Mean Square Residual			0.050			
N			4479			

Notes:

S.E. – standard error; CI – confidence interval.

Analysis performed with Mplus 8.6: weighted least squares mean and variance adjusted (WLSMV) estimation was used in order to account for categorical (binary) nature of the data and non-normality of the not-binary item. All items declared as categorical, parametrization – Delta, link function – Probit. Inter-item correlations included into the model: At home: Musical instruments vs. At home: Works of art = 0.163, At home: Three or more computers vs. At home: Dishwasher = 0.275.

Table 2.3b. Weighted least squares mean and variance adjusted estimates and fit statistics for single-factor models of the social-economic-cultural index items: 8th grade, 2014.

Items	8 th grade, 2014					
	Estimate	S.E.	p-value	Resid. variance	Std. estimate	R ²
Number of books at home	1.000	--	--	0.437	0.750	0.563
At home: Own books	0.769	0.043	0.000	0.667	0.577	0.333
At home: Encyclopedia	0.995	0.039	0.000	0.442	0.747	0.558
At home: Musical instruments	0.642	0.034	0.000	0.768	0.482	0.232
At home: Works of art	0.528	0.036	0.000	0.843	0.397	0.157
At home: Three or more computers	0.321	0.034	0.000	0.942	0.241	0.058
At home: Dishwasher	0.385	0.035	0.000	0.916	0.289	0.084
Free meal at school	0.639	0.035	0.000	0.77	0.479	0.23
Private tutor	0.349	0.040	0.000	0.931	0.262	0.069
Model characteristics						
X²			167.245 (df=25, p<0.001)			
Comparative Fit Index			0.962			
Tucker-Lewis Index			0.945			
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation			0.039 (90% CI: 0.033-0.045, p (probability RMSEA <= .05) = 0.999			
Standardized Root Mean Square Residual			0.049			
N			3763			

Notes:

S.E. – standard error; CI – confidence interval.

Analysis performed with Mplus 8.6: weighted least squares mean and variance adjusted (WLSMV) estimation was used in order to account for categorical (binary) nature of the data and non-normality of the not-binary item. All items declared as categorical, parametrization – Delta, link function – Probit. Inter-item correlations included into the model: At home: Musical instruments vs. At home: Works of art = 0.100, At home: Three or more computers vs. At home: Dishwasher = 0.209.

Table 2.3c. Weighted least squares mean and variance adjusted estimates and fit statistics for single-factor models of the social-economic-cultural index items: 8th grade, 2015.

Items	8 th grade, 2015					
	Estimate	S.E.	p-value	Resid. variance	Std. estimate	R ²
Number of books at home	1.000	--	--	0.433	0.753	0.567
At home: Own books	0.819	0.045	0.000	0.619	0.617	0.381
At home: Encyclopedia	0.979	0.043	0.000	0.456	0.737	0.544
At home: Musical instruments	0.681	0.038	0.000	0.737	0.513	0.263
At home: Works of art	0.484	0.037	0.000	0.867	0.365	0.133
At home: Three or more computers	0.304	0.035	0.000	0.947	0.229	0.053
At home: Dishwasher	0.361	0.036	0.000	0.926	0.272	0.074
Free meal at school	0.656	0.038	0.000	0.756	0.494	0.244
Private tutor	0.291	0.039	0.000	0.952	0.219	0.048
Model characteristics						
X²			107.231 (df=25, p<0.001)			
Comparative Fit Index			0.975			
Tucker-Lewis Index			0.964			
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation			0.031 (90% CI: 0.025-0.037, p (probability RMSEA <= .05) = 1.000			
Standardized Root Mean Square Residual			0.041			
N			3482			

Notes:

S.E. – standard error; CI – confidence interval.

Analysis performed with Mplus 8.6: weighted least squares mean and variance adjusted (WLSMV) estimation was used in order to account for categorical (binary) nature of the data and non-normality of the not-binary item. All items declared as categorical, parametrization – Delta, link function – Probit. Inter-item correlations included into the model: At home: Musical instruments vs. At home: Works of art = 0.086, At home: Three or more computers vs. At home: Dishwasher = 0.180.

Table 2.3d. Weighted least squares mean and variance adjusted estimates and fit statistics for single-factor models of the social-economic-cultural index items: 6th grade, 2016.

Items	6 th grade, 2016					
	Estimate	S.E.	p-value	Resid. variance	Std. estimate	R ²
Number of books at home	1.000	--	--	0.528	0.687	0.472
At home: Own books	0.755	0.067	0.000	0.73	0.519	0.27
At home: Encyclopedia	1.122	0.065	0.000	0.405	0.771	0.595
At home: Musical instruments	0.562	0.049	0.000	0.851	0.386	0.149
At home: Works of art	0.473	0.050	0.000	0.894	0.325	0.106
At home: Three or more computers	0.302	0.046	0.000	0.957	0.208	0.043
At home: Dishwasher	0.315	0.046	0.000	0.953	0.216	0.047
Free meal at school	0.728	0.052	0.000	0.75	0.5	0.25
Private tutor	0.108	0.055	0.047	0.994	0.075	0.006
Model characteristics						
X ²			70.331 (df=25, p<0.001)			
Comparative Fit Index			0.974			
Tucker-Lewis Index			0.963			
Root Mean Square Error of Approximation			0.026 (90% CI: 0.019-0.033, p (probability RMSEA <= .05) = 1.000			
Standardized Root Mean Square Residual			0.040			
N			2710			

Notes:

S.E. – standard error; CI – confidence interval.

Analysis performed with Mplus 8.6: weighted least squares mean and variance adjusted (WLSMV) estimation was used in order to account for categorical (binary) nature of the data and non-normality of the not-binary item. All items declared as categorical, parametrization – Delta, link function – Probit. Inter-item correlations included into the model: At home: Musical instruments vs. At home: Works of art = 0.029, At home: Three or more computers vs. At home: Dishwasher = 0.203

Table 2.4. MSEP value for different number of dimensions across the four datasets.

Dataset year	Number of dimensions					
	0	1	2	3	4	5
2012	3.863278	3.859874	3.858670	3.858678	3.858906	3.859101
2014	3.839623	3.836934	3.836340	3.836623	3.837070	3.837131
2015	3.849389	3.846234	3.845809	3.845903	3.846251	3.846403
2016	3.853725	3.851673	3.851164	3.851340	3.851512	3.851868

Table 2.5a. Coordinates, relative contributions, squared cosines, v.test and eta squared estimates from the 2-dimensional MCA solution for 2012 NSSA data.

Category	Dimension 1					Dimension 2				
	Coord.	Ctrb.	Cos ²	V.test	Eta ²	Coord.	Ctrb.	Cos ²	V.test	Eta ²
Books:1-10	1.151	9.146	0.220	31.324	0.461	1.191	15.949	0.235	32.408	0.345
Books:11-25	0.471	3.028	0.087	19.687		-0.237	1.252	0.022	-9.918	
Books:26-100	-0.253	1.030	0.032	-11.908		-0.474	5.889	0.112	-22.308	
Books:101-200	-0.709	3.438	0.083	-19.193		-0.134	0.201	0.003	-3.631	
Books:>200	-1.062	5.786	0.134	-24.402		0.696	4.050	0.057	15.995	
Home:book:No	1.244	4.840	0.109	21.823	0.106	1.987	20.113	0.278	34.853	0.271
Home:book:Yes	-0.086	0.333	0.109	-21.823		-0.137	1.383	0.278	-34.853	
Home_ency:No	1.097	14.493	0.403	42.107	0.396	0.413	3.340	0.057	15.837	0.056
Home_ency:Yes	-0.361	4.765	0.403	-42.107		-0.136	1.098	0.057	-15.837	
Home_musi:No	0.470	5.864	0.272	34.513	0.266	-0.025	0.026	0.001	-1.815	0.001
Home_musi:Yes	-0.566	7.074	0.272	-34.513		0.030	0.032	0.001	1.815	
Home_arta:No	0.579	5.285	0.164	26.819	0.161	0.205	1.079	0.021	9.493	0.020
Home_arta:Yes	-0.277	2.528	0.164	-26.819		-0.098	0.516	0.021	-9.493	
Home_3com:No	0.271	2.419	0.158	26.259	0.154	-0.338	6.135	0.246	-32.768	0.240
Home_3com:Yes	-0.568	5.071	0.158	-26.259		0.709	12.865	0.246	32.768	
Home_dish:No	0.275	2.465	0.158	26.307	0.155	-0.317	5.359	0.211	-30.392	0.206
Home_dish:Yes	-0.563	5.052	0.158	-26.307		0.650	10.986	0.211	30.392	
FreeMeal:Yes	0.731	7.998	0.238	32.616	0.238	-0.025	0.015	0.000	-1.106	0.000
FreeMeal:No	-0.325	3.557	0.238	-32.616		0.011	0.007	0.000	1.106	
Tutor:No	0.200	1.460	0.120	23.165	0.120	-0.202	2.431	0.122	-23.418	0.122
Tutor:Yes	-0.599	4.368	0.120	-23.165		0.605	7.273	0.122	23.418	

Table 2.5b. Coordinates, relative contributions, squared cosines, v.test and eta squared estimates from the 2-dimensional MCA solution for 2014 NSSA data.

Category	Dimension 1					Dimension 2				
	Coord.	Ctrb.	Cos ²	V.test	Eta ²	Coord.	Ctrb.	Cos ²	V.test	Eta ²
Books:1-10	1.327	12.874	0.330	35.162	0.539	1.102	14.859	0.228	29.212	0.396
Books:11-25	0.337	1.528	0.046	13.188		-0.559	7.020	0.127	-21.857	
Books:26-100	-0.274	1.081	0.034	-11.251		-0.389	3.632	0.068	-15.946	
Books:101-200	-0.774	3.825	0.096	-18.941		0.187	0.373	0.006	4.576	
Books:>200	-1.069	5.726	0.138	-22.789		0.766	4.915	0.071	16.326	
Home:book:No	1.573	8.178	0.192	26.692	0.189	1.691	15.805	0.222	28.695	0.219
Home:book:Yes	-0.120	0.626	0.192	-26.692		-0.129	1.210	0.222	-28.695	
Home_ency:No	1.156	15.143	0.436	40.250	0.431	0.396	2.966	0.051	13.776	0.050
Home_ency:Yes	-0.372	4.877	0.436	-40.250		-0.127	0.955	0.051	-13.776	
Home_musi:No	0.476	5.687	0.268	31.586	0.265	-0.036	0.056	0.002	-2.415	0.002
Home_musi:Yes	-0.557	6.642	0.268	-31.586		0.043	0.065	0.002	2.415	
Home_arta:No	0.677	6.476	0.202	27.444	0.200	0.169	0.673	0.013	6.841	0.012
Home_arta:Yes	-0.296	2.832	0.202	-27.444		-0.074	0.294	0.013	-6.841	
Home_3com:No	0.320	2.323	0.098	19.133	0.097	-0.458	7.931	0.201	-27.340	0.199
Home_3com:Yes	-0.304	2.201	0.098	-19.133		0.434	7.515	0.201	27.340	
Home_dish:No	0.270	2.106	0.122	21.238	0.120	-0.365	6.451	0.223	-28.745	0.220
Home_dish:Yes	-0.444	3.468	0.122	-21.238		0.601	10.623	0.223	28.745	
FreeMeal:Yes	0.818	8.345	0.246	30.384	0.245	-0.256	1.363	0.024	-9.496	0.024
FreeMeal:No	-0.300	3.063	0.246	-30.384		0.094	0.500	0.024	9.496	
Tutor:No	0.121	0.555	0.065	15.578	0.065	-0.193	2.370	0.165	-24.882	0.165
Tutor:Yes	-0.533	2.443	0.065	-15.578		0.851	10.424	0.165	24.882	

Table 2.5c. Coordinates, relative contributions, squared cosines, v.test and eta squared estimates from the 2-dimensional MCA solution for 2015 NSSA data.

Category	Dimension 1					Dimension 2				
	Coord.	Ctrb.	Cos ²	V.test	Eta ²	Coord.	Ctrb.	Cos ²	V.test	Eta ²
Books:1-10	1.464	14.753	0.373	35.868	0.550	0.999	11.883	0.174	24.475	0.366
Books:11-25	0.315	1.316	0.040	11.692		-0.501	5.764	0.100	-18.601	
Books:26-100	-0.299	1.343	0.043	-12.126		-0.444	5.121	0.094	-18.004	
Books:101-200	-0.743	3.386	0.084	-17.028		0.379	1.527	0.022	8.695	
Books:>200	-0.947	4.932	0.121	-20.387		0.749	5.326	0.075	16.109	
Home:book:No	1.698	9.348	0.218	27.334	0.215	1.667	15.583	0.210	26.832	0.207
Home:book:Yes	-0.126	0.696	0.218	-27.334		-0.124	1.160	0.210	-26.832	
Home_ency:No	1.235	15.685	0.435	38.669	0.430	0.315	1.763	0.028	9.856	0.028
Home_ency:Yes	-0.348	4.418	0.435	-38.669		-0.089	0.496	0.028	-9.856	
Home_musi:No	0.483	5.968	0.286	31.302	0.281	-0.088	0.341	0.009	-5.692	0.009
Home_musi:Yes	-0.583	7.204	0.286	-31.302		0.106	0.412	0.009	5.692	
Home_arta:No	0.615	5.474	0.172	24.274	0.169	0.117	0.341	0.006	4.608	0.006
Home_arta:Yes	-0.275	2.447	0.172	-24.274		-0.052	0.153	0.006	-4.608	
Home_3com:No	0.265	1.773	0.084	16.934	0.082	-0.410	7.349	0.201	-26.214	0.197
Home_3com:Yes	-0.311	2.082	0.084	-16.934		0.482	8.632	0.201	26.214	
Home_dish:No	0.267	1.965	0.104	18.879	0.102	-0.402	7.707	0.236	-28.425	0.232
Home_dish:Yes	-0.384	2.826	0.104	-18.879		0.578	11.083	0.236	28.425	
FreeMeal:Yes	0.965	9.312	0.256	29.682	0.253	-0.041	0.030	0.000	-1.271	0.000
FreeMeal:No	-0.262	2.532	0.256	-29.682		0.011	0.008	0.000	1.271	
Tutor:No	0.137	0.654	0.054	13.746	0.054	-0.256	3.943	0.189	-25.668	0.189
Tutor:Yes	-0.396	1.887	0.054	-13.746		0.739	11.379	0.189	25.668	

Table 2.5d. Coordinates, relative contributions, squared cosines, v.test and eta squared estimates from the 2-dimensional MCA solution for 2016 NSSA data.

Category	Dimension 1					Dimension 2				
	Coord.	Ctrb.	Cos ²	V.test	Eta ²	Coord.	Ctrb.	Cos ²	V.test	Eta ²
Books:1-10	1.455	15.125	0.341	30.336	0.523	0.527	3.253	0.045	10.984	0.167
Books:11-25	0.320	1.746	0.051	11.687		-0.294	2.421	0.043	-10.744	
Books:26-100	-0.431	3.180	0.092	-15.781		-0.213	1.273	0.023	-7.797	
Books:101-200	-0.755	3.721	0.083	-14.944		0.126	0.169	0.002	2.486	
Books:>200	-0.917	3.259	0.069	-13.591		1.051	7.019	0.090	15.572	
Home:book:No	1.807	8.740	0.181	21.983	0.178	1.658	12.067	0.153	20.167	0.150
Home:book:Yes	-0.099	0.477	0.181	-21.983		-0.091	0.659	0.153	-20.167	
Home_ency:No	1.246	18.505	0.470	35.508	0.465	0.161	0.510	0.008	4.600	0.008
Home_ency:Yes	-0.373	5.544	0.470	-35.508		-0.048	0.153	0.008	-4.600	
Home_musi:No	0.420	4.694	0.189	22.522	0.187	-0.089	0.344	0.008	-4.764	0.008
Home_musi:Yes	-0.446	4.982	0.189	-22.522		0.094	0.366	0.008	4.764	
Home_arta:No	0.602	5.254	0.143	19.569	0.141	0.381	3.456	0.057	12.391	0.057
Home_arta:Yes	-0.235	2.050	0.143	-19.569		-0.149	1.348	0.057	-12.391	
Home_3com:No	0.283	2.084	0.082	14.815	0.081	-0.504	10.819	0.260	-26.354	0.256
Home_3com:Yes	-0.286	2.102	0.082	-14.815		0.508	10.912	0.260	26.354	
Home_dish:No	0.269	1.946	0.080	14.579	0.078	-0.559	13.767	0.344	-30.279	0.338
Home_dish:Yes	-0.292	2.109	0.080	-14.579		0.606	14.920	0.344	30.279	
FreeMeal:Yes	0.996	11.083	0.275	27.231	0.274	0.172	0.540	0.008	4.695	0.008
FreeMeal:No	-0.275	3.061	0.275	-27.231		-0.047	0.149	0.008	-4.695	
Tutor:No	0.038	0.062	0.007	4.216	0.007	-0.204	2.890	0.187	-22.511	0.187
Tutor:Yes	-0.172	0.277	0.007	-4.216		0.916	12.966	0.187	22.511	

Table 2.6a. Aggregate SEC_I Index: Descriptives

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	4479	3763	3482	2710
Missing	0	0	0	0
Min - Max	-1.41 – 1.23	-1.61 – 1.33	-1.66 – 1.28	-1.54 – 1.15
Mean (SD)	-0.01(0.52)	-0.01(0.06)	-0.01(0.60)	-0.02(0.53)
Median	0.03	0.00	0.02	0.01
Skewness (st.error)	-0.08(0.04)	-0.09(0.04)	-0.17(0.04)	-0.22(0.05)
Kurtosis (st.error)	-0.42(0.07)	-0.42(0.08)	-0.37(0.08)	-0.33(0.09)
ICC (school)	0.23	0.2	0.24	0.2

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in SEC_I Index accounted by school-level differences.

Table 2.6b. Two-Dimensional (SEC_D1 and SEC_D2) Index: Descriptives

	SEC_D1				SEC_D2			
	2012	2014	2015	2016 ¹	2012	2014	2015	2016 ¹
N	4479	3763	3482	2710	4479	3763	3482	2710
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Min - Max	-1.40 – 1.02	-1.53 – 0.91	-1.63 – 0.83	-1.71 – 0.74	-0.52 – 1.63	-0.65 – 1.49	-0.59 – 1.38	-0.61 – 1.47
Mean (SD)	0.00(0.48)	0.00(0.49)	0.00(0.49)	0.00(0.46)	0.00(0.37)	0.00(0.38)	0.00(0.37)	0.00(0.36)
Median	0.02	0.05	0.07	0.09	-0.07	-0.03	0.00	-0.02
Skewness (st.error)	-0.24(0.04)	-0.52(0.04)	-0.73(0.04)	-0.85(0.05)	0.84(0.04)	0.55(0.04)	0.52(0.04)	0.43(0.05)
Kurtosis (st.error)	-0.43(0.07)	-0.17(0.08)	0.15(0.08)	0.42(0.09)	0.68(0.07)	-0.06(0.08)	-0.07(0.08)	-0.03(0.09)
ICC (school)	0.23	0.19	0.23	0.19	0.07	0.04	0.04	0.04

Note. ¹ – 2016 dataset contains responses of the 6th grade students, while the rest of the databases contain responses of the 8th graders. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in SEC_D1 and SEC_D2 Indexes accounted by school-level differences.

Table 2.6c. Categorical SEC_C Index: Descriptives

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	4479	3763	3482	2710
Missing	0	0	0	0
1st quintile (n)	-1.40 / -0.42 (896)	-1.53 / -0.43 (756)	-1.63 / -0.39 (696)	-1.71 / -0.38 (548)
2nd quintile (n)	-0.42 / -0.12 (899)	-0.43 / -0.07 (756)	-0.39 / -0.06 (698)	-0.39 / -0.03 (538)
3rd quintile (n)	-0.12 / 0.16 (895)	-0.07 / 0.18 (752)	-0.06 / 0.18 (713)	-0.03 / 0.19 (546)
4th quintile (n)	0.16 / 0.42 (893)	0.18 / 0.42 (750)	0.18 / 0.42 (693)	0.19 / 0.41 (536)
5th quintile (n)	0.42 / 1.02 (896)	0.42 / 0.91 (749)	0.42 / 0.83 (682)	0.41 / 0.74 (542)
ICC (school)	0.2	0.19	0.22	0.18

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in SEC_C Index accounted by school-level differences.

Table 2.7a. SEC_I Index: Construct validity and internal consistency

Correlates	SEC_I			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
Students' pocket-money	.18	.19	.14	.14
Mother's job	.14	.16	.18	.12
Father's job	.11	.12	.13	.11
Mother's job (in the field of management)	.21	.25	-	-
Father's job (in a field of management)	.25	.26	-	-
Mother education	.43	.42	.35	.37
Father education	.39	.38	.35	.35

Note. Pearson's r correlation coefficients are presented in the table. All correlations are statistically significant at the .001 level.

Table 2.7b. SEC_D1 Index: Construct validity and internal consistency

Correlates	SEC_D1			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
Students' pocket-money	.21	.22	.17	.16
Mother's job	.15	.17	.19	.13
Father's job	.12	.13	.14	.11
Mother's job (in the field of management)	.23	.30	-	-
Father's job (in a field of management)	.27	.28	-	-
Mother education	.44	.42	.36	.37
Father education	.40	.37	.35	.34
Estimate of internal consistency of items				
	.58	.60	.60	.54

Note. Pearson's r correlation coefficients are presented in the table. All correlations are statistically significant at the .001 level.

Table 2.8. Histograms for SEC_I and SEC_D1, SEC_D2 Indexes.

2012 (8th grade) 2014 (8th grade) 2015 (8th grade) 2016 (6th grade)

SEC_I

SEC_D1

SEC_D2

Figure 2.1a. MCA solution for 2012 (8th grade) items measuring SEC.

Figure 2.1b. MCA solution for 2014 (8th grade) items measuring SEC.

Figure 2.1c. MCA solution for 2015 (8th grade) items measuring SEC.

Figure 2.1d. MCA solution for 2016 (6th grade) items measuring SEC.

3. ASSESSING STUDENTS' MOTIVATIONAL, EMOTIONAL, AND SOCIAL FUNCTIONING AT SCHOOL

3.1 Academic self-concept

3.1.1 Theoretical conceptualization of the construct

Academic self-concept is one component of a multidimensional, hierarchical model of self-concept, consisting of academic, social, emotional and physical self-concepts (Marsh & Craven, 2006, Marsh&Martin, 2011, Shavelson, 1976). This model makes an important distinction between general self-concept and its different components. Research shows that the most significant relations of self-concept are between specific components of self-concept and specific outcomes, which are most logically related - for example academic achievement is correlated with academic self-concept but is nearly unrelated with non-academic components of self-concept or more global self-concept construct (Marsh & Craven, 2006, Marsh&Martin 2011).

A key component of academic self-concept is perceived academic competence. In its broadest sense academic self-concept is individuals' knowledge and perceptions about themselves in the context of achievement (Bong & Skaalvik, 2003) or school subjects in general (Brunner, Keller, Hornung, Reichert, & Martin, 2009; Marsh, Trautwein, Lüdtke, Köller, & Baumert, 2005). Specific operationalisations of academic self-concept vary across studies, however the construct generally refers to subjective answers to the question "Can I succeed in this task (learning at school)?" (Eccles et al., 1993).

Students' self-perceptions play an important role in their achievement and adjustment during childhood and adolescence. Academic self-concept is related to a range of academic outcomes. Students with high self-concept tend to show higher academic results (Arens et. al, 2017, Valentine et al., 2004), expresses greater interest in the subject (Marsh, Trautwein, Lüdtke, Köller, & Baumert, 2005), are more engaged in extracurricular activities (Nagengast et. al., 2011), more often express specific occupational aspirations and intentions to study or work in a particular subject-related field (Ireson & Hallam, 2009, Nagengast et. al., 2011). Research also shows that positive self-concept is particularly beneficial in cases of anxiety, impaired motivation, and is important for facilitating subsequent performance following failure (Marsh, Craven, 2006).

An important question that is raised in contemporary research – what goes first – academic self-concept or academic achievement? Number of studies found that the relation between academic self-concept and academic achievement often is reciprocal: higher academic achievement enhances academic self-concept and reverse - higher academic self-concept enhances academic achievement (Marsh & Craven, 2006; Marsh & Martin, 2011; Marsh et al., 2005, Vu et. al, 2021).

Such findings, that academic self-concept and academic achievement are reciprocally related and mutually reinforcing, has important implications for educators. Teachers should strive to improve simultaneously both academic self-concept and achievement, because if teachers focus on only one of these constructs, then both are likely to suffer (Marsh, Martin, 2011).

3.1.2 Operationalization of the construct in NSSA data

The operationalization of academic self-concept in NSSA data is in line with the conceptualization of the phenomenon as a unidimensional construct covering such aspects of self-concept as self-confidence, focus on learning, using of different ways to complete a task. Respondents were asked to express their agreement to such statements as:

- You are not afraid of difficulties during learning;
- You trust in your own strengths while learning;
- You know the different ways to do not only the tasks you like, but also the ones that are difficult or boring;
- You are good at focusing on learning.

Each item was assessed on a 4-point ratio scale: 1- *completely disagree*, 2- *disagree*, 3- *agree*, 4- *completely agree*. The total score for the scale is calculated by averaging the responses for four items. The mean score represents the level of student's academic self-concept. Higher scores indicate higher academic self-concept. The same items and identical response scale were used to assess academic self-concept across different rounds of NSSA (2012-2016) (see table 3.1.1).

3.1.3 Descriptive statistics

Descriptives for the scale are presented in tables 3.1.2 and 3.1.3. Mean scores are between 2.8 and 3.0, when the maximum values are 4. Median scores are 2.8 (except in 2016, median score is 3.0), indicating that half of participants indicated that their academic self-concept is higher than that value of 2.8.

Values of skewness are between -0.33 and 0.16 across different rounds of NSSA indicating that data are a little skewed to the left side (2016) or right side (2012 and 2015). However, values of skewness are between -0.5 and 0.5 indicated that distributions of academic self-concept scale are fairly symmetric across all rounds. Values of kurtosis are between 0.13 and 0.80. Thus, a normal distribution of this scale data could be assumed.

Individual differences are the main source of variance in academic self-concept. Differences between schools account for 2.8 % to 4.4 % of variance in academic self-concept in 2012 – 2015. Differences between schools were not observed in year 2016 (see ICC scores in table 3.1.2).

3.1.4 Scale validity in NSSA data

Structural validity. The unidimensional nature of the scale was supported by the findings from exploratory factor analysis (principal axis factoring) for the four academic self-concept items (see table 3.1.4). Across all four datasets, a single factor with eigenvalue > 1 was identified. The total variance explained by the single factor ranged from 46.69 % to 57.39 %. All item loadings were above the common cut-off point of 0.40 in all datasets.

Convergent/ divergent validity. The findings indicated moderate to strong positive correlations between academic self-concept and such teaching characteristics as: autonomy support, competence support and relatedness support (between 0.23 and 0.58). Strong positive correlations are observed between academic self-concept and academic task value (between 0.67 and 0.78), moderate positive correlations - between academic self-concept and emotional school engagement (between 0.23 and 0.37) and relationships with parents (between 0.26 and 0.34). Correlations between academic self-concept and victimization in bullying are negative, from weak to moderate (between -0.23 and -0.09). Correlations between academic self-concept and academic achievements are from weak to moderate positive: between 0.10 to 0.25 (see table 3.1.5).

Internal consistency. Acceptable internal consistency was observed for the scale across all rounds of NSSA, Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.71 to 0.81.

Table 3.1.1 Academic self-concept: Scale structure and syntax

Intro: Do you agree with these statements:			
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
A1d/You not afraid of difficulties during learning/ <i>Nebijai mokymosi sunkumų</i>	A1d/You not afraid of difficulties during learning/ <i>Nebijai mokymosi sunkumų</i>	A1d/You not afraid of difficulties during learning/ <i>Nebijai mokymosi sunkumų</i>	A1d/You not afraid of difficulties during learning/ <i>Nebijai mokymosi sunkumų</i>
A1e/You trust in your own strengths while learning/ <i>Mokydamasis pasitiki savo jėgomis</i>	A1e/You trust in your own strengths while learning/ <i>Mokydamasis pasitiki savo jėgomis</i>	A1e/You trust in your own strengths while learning/ <i>Mokydamasis pasitiki savo jėgomis</i>	A1e/You trust in your own strengths while learning/ <i>Mokydamasis pasitiki savo jėgomis</i>
A5b/You know the different ways to do not only the tasks I like, but also the ones that are difficult or boring/ <i>Žinai įvairių būdų, padedančių atlikti ne tik tas užduotis, kurios Tau patinka, bet ir tas, kurios sunkios ar nuobodžios</i>	A5b/You know the different ways to do not only the tasks I like, but also the ones that are difficult or boring/ <i>Žinai įvairių būdų, padedančių atlikti ne tik tas užduotis, kurios Tau patinka, bet ir tas, kurios sunkios ar nuobodžios</i>	A5b/You know the different ways to do not only the tasks I like, but also the ones that are difficult or boring/ <i>Žinai įvairių būdų, padedančių atlikti ne tik tas užduotis, kurios Tau patinka, bet ir tas, kurios sunkios ar nuobodžios</i>	A5b/You know the different ways to do not only the tasks I like, but also the ones that are difficult or boring/ <i>Žinai įvairių būdų, padedančių atlikti ne tik tas užduotis, kurios Tau patinka, bet ir tas, kurios sunkios ar nuobodžios</i>
A5a/You are good at focusing on learning/ <i>Tau gerai sekasi sutelkti dėmesį mokantis</i>	A5a/You are good at focusing on learning/ <i>Tau gerai sekasi sutelkti dėmesį mokantis</i>	A5a/You are good at focusing on learning/ <i>Tau gerai sekasi sutelkti dėmesį mokantis</i>	A5a/You are good at focusing on learning/ <i>Tau gerai sekasi sutelkti dėmesį mokantis</i>
Response scale:		1. <i>Completely disagree</i>	
		2. <i>Disagree</i>	
		3. <i>Agree</i>	
		4. <i>Completely agree</i>	
Missings:		98, 99	
Scale total			
AcSELF=MEAN(A1d, A1e, A5b,	AcSELF=MEAN(A1d, A1e, A5b,	AcSELF=MEAN(A1d, A1e, A5b,	AcSELF=MEAN(A1d, A1e, A5b,

Intro: Do you agree with these statements:

2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
A5a)	A5a)	A5a)	A5a)

Table 3.1.2. Academic self-concept: Scale descriptives

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	991	830	431	430
Missing	3488	2933	3051	2380
Min - Max	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4
Mean (SD)	2.84 (0.47)	2.82 (0.51)	2.87 (0.53)	2.99 (0.55)
Median	2.8	2.8	2.8	3.0
Skewness (st.error)	-0.001 (0.08)	0.093 (0.09)	0.157 (0.12)	-0.33 (0.12)
Kurtosis (st.error)	0.64 (0.16)	0.57 (0.17)	0.13 (0.24)	0.80 (0.24)
ICC (school)	0.028	0.044	0.028	-*

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in academic self-concept accounted by school-level differences.

*- no differences between schools are observed.

Table 3.1.3. Academic self-concept: Histograms

2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
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Table 3.1.4. Academic self-concept: Factor structure

	Results of exploratory factor analysis			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
No of factors with eigenvalue >1	1	1	1	1
Total variance explained by factor 1, %	46.69	52.50	52.23	57.39
No of items for factor 1	5	5	5	5
Mix – max factor loadings	0.50 - 0.61	0.50 - 0.76	0.43 - 0.76	0.61- 0.79

Note. Principal axis factoring is applied to evaluate factor structure of a scale.

Table 3.1.5. Academic self-concept: Construct validity and internal consistency

Correlates	Academic self-concept			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
Mathematics achievement	0.203**	0.194**	0.135**	0.246**
Reading achievement	0.104**	0.158**	0.141**	0.108*
Academic value	0.674**	0.711**	0.683**	0.776**
Emotional engagement	0.229**	0.371**	0.329**	0.359**

Victimization in bullying	-0.092**	-0.198**	-0.106*	-0.225**
Autonomy support	0.307**	0.455**	0.423**	0.568**
Competence support	0.296**	0.417**	0.464**	0.509**
Relatedness support	0.296**	0.430**	0.405**	0.583**
Parents academic support	0.261**	0.366**	-	-
Communication with parents	0.273**	0.337**	0.286**	0.288**
Cronbach's alpha	0.71	0.77	0.77	0.81

Note. Pearson's r correlation coefficients are presented in the table. ** - Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level, * - Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

3.2 Emotional school engagement

3.2.1 Theoretical conceptualization of the construct

Emotional school engagement is one component of a multidimensional construct consisting of behavioural, emotional, cognitive, and social school engagement (Wang et al. 2017; Li and Lerner, 2013). Although the emotional, behavioural, cognitive, and social components of school engagement are often explored separately, they mutually influence each other over time. It has been suggested that emotional engagement plays a significant and distinctive role in the ways in which students engage in academic activities as their school career progresses (Li and Lerner, 2013).

Emotional school engagement encompasses the overall positive affective reactions and the enjoyment of, and value attributed to school activities (Finn, 1989). Emotional engagement in school is thought to play a central role in adolescents' academic achievement and adjustment. Studies show that school engagement can be a protective asset that decreases the chance of negative behaviours and increases the likelihood of academic success. Students who are not engaged in school emotionally may be able to earn good grades, but they are at risk for poor mental health outcomes, which can affect various measures of adolescents' academic success (Wang et al. 2015).

It has been suggested that emotional engagement in school activities is a substantial prerequisite for students' effort, achievement and persistence in studying. Students who regard school as vital and valuable and consider themselves to be members of the school community have been found to receive higher grades and to complete school successfully. Moreover, a strong sense of belonging at school is related to positive future orientations in adolescence and good overall development in adolescence (Ulmanen et al. 2016).

The quality of interaction with teachers and other students plays an important yet different role in the construction of the dimensions of emotional engagement.

The significance of informational support received from peers in the construction of emotional engagement in schoolwork is important in terms of developing a pedagogy that is more engaging and utilises peer interaction as a resource for learning, not just for climate or school satisfaction (Ulmanen et al. 2016).

Failure to engage in school may lead adolescents to associate with delinquent friends, devalue academics, and feel alienated from peers and teachers, which in turn increases their disengagement from school (Morrison, Robertson, Laurie, & Kelly, 2002).

3.2.2 Operationalization of the construct in NSSA data

The operationalization of emotional engagement in NSSA data is in line with the conceptualization of the phenomenon as a unidimensional construct covering such emotional aspects as safety at school and positive feelings towards school, class, and

learning. Respondents were asked to express their agreement to such statements as:

- Feel safe at school;
- Love being in school;
- Enjoy studying in school;
- Feel good in class.

Each item was assessed on a 4-point ratio scale: 1- *completely disagree*, 2- *disagree*, 3- *agree*, 4- *completely agree*. The total score for the scale is calculated by averaging the responses for four items. The mean score represents the level of student's emotional engagement. Higher scores indicate higher emotional engagement. The same items and identical response scale were used to assess emotional engagement across different rounds of NSSA (2012-2016) (see table 3.2.1).

3.2.3 Descriptive statistics

Descriptives for the scale are presented in tables 3.2.2 and 3.2.3. Mean scores are between 2.8 and 2.97, when the maximum values are 4. Median scores are 3, indicating that half of participants reported that their emotional engagement is higher than the value of 3.

Values of skewness are negative (between -0.58 and -0.33) across different rounds of NSSA indicating that data are a little skewed to the left side. Values of kurtosis are between 0.39 and 0.81. Thus, a normal distribution of this scale data could be assumed.

Individual differences are the main source of variance in emotional engagement. Differences between schools account for 6.7% to 10.4 % of variance in emotional engagement (see ICC scores in table 3.2.2).

3.2.4 Scale validity in NSSA data

Structural validity. The unidimensional nature of the scale was supported by the findings from exploratory factor analysis (principal axis factoring) for the four emotional engagement items (see table 3.2.4). Across all four datasets, a single factor with eigenvalue > 1 was identified. The total variance explained by the single factor ranged from 39.74 % to 47.49 %. All item loadings were above the common cut-off point of 0.40 in all datasets.

Convergent/ divergent validity. The findings indicated moderate positive correlations between emotional engagement and teaching characteristics: autonomy support, competence support and relatedness support (between 0.29 and 0.41). From week to moderate positive correlations are observed between emotional engagement and students' functioning at school characteristics: academics self-concept and academic task value (between 0.17 and 0.37). Correlation between emotional engagement and victimization in bullying are moderate negative (between -0.33 and -0.30). Moderate positive correlations are observed between emotional engagement and relationships with parents (between 0.28 and 0.32). Week positive correlations are observed

between emotional engagement and academic achievement (between 0.04 and 0.13). All correlations are significant except correlations between emotional engagement and mathematics achievement in year 2014 (see table 3.1.5).

Internal consistency. Acceptable internal consistency was observed for the scale across all rounds of NSSA, Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.72 to 0.78.

Table 3.2.1. Emotional school engagement: Scale structure and syntax

Intro: What do you think:			
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
B23a/ At school, you feel safe <i>[Mokykloje Tu jautiesi saugus]</i>	B24a/ At school, you feel safe <i>[Mokykloje Tu jautiesi saugus]</i>	B21a/ At school, you feel safe <i>[Mokykloje Tu jautiesi saugus]</i>	B21a/ At school, you feel safe <i>[Mokykloje Tu jautiesi saugus]</i>
B23b/ You love being in school / guardians <i>[Tau patinka būti mokykloje]</i>	B24b/ You love being in school / guardians <i>[Tau patinka būti mokykloje]</i>	B21b/ You love being in school / guardians <i>[Tau patinka būti mokykloje]</i>	B21b/ You love being in school / guardians <i>[Tau patinka būti mokykloje]</i>
B23c/ You enjoy studying in your school <i>[Tau patinka mokytis savo mokykloje]</i>	B24c/ You enjoy studying in your school <i>[Tau patinka mokytis savo mokykloje]</i>	B21c/ You enjoy studying in your school <i>[Tau patinka mokytis savo mokykloje]</i>	B21c/ You enjoy studying in your school <i>[Tau patinka mokytis savo mokykloje]</i>
B24c/ You feel good in class <i>[Klasėje jautiesi gerai]</i>	B25c/ You feel good in class <i>[Klasėje jautiesi gerai]</i>	B22c/ You feel good in class <i>[Klasėje jautiesi gerai]</i>	B22c/ You feel good in class <i>[Klasėje jautiesi gerai]</i>
Response scale:		1. <i>Completely disagree</i>	
		2. <i>Disagree</i>	
		3. <i>Agree</i>	
		4. <i>Completely agree</i>	
Missings:		98, 99	
Scale total			
EmoENG = MEAN(B23a, B23b, B23c, B24c)	EmoENG = MEAN(B24a, B24b, B24c, B25c)	EmoENG = MEAN(B21a, B21b, B21c, B22c)	EmoENG = MEAN(B21a, B21b, B21c, B22c)

Table 3.2.2. Emotional school engagement: Scale descriptives

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	4463	3750	3445	2695
Missing	16	13	37	15
Min - Max	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4
Mean (SD)	2.8 (0.54)	2.81 (0.61)	2.85 (0.58)	2.97 (0.58)
Median	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Skewness (st.error)	-0.45 (0.04)	-0.33 (0.04)	-0.43 (0.04)	-0.58 (0.05)
Kurtosis (st.error)	0.81 (0.07)	0.39 (0.08)	0.59 (0.08)	0.7 (0.09)
ICC (school)	0.085	0.104	0.093	0.067

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in emotional engagement accounted by school-level differences.

Table 3.2.3. Emotional school engagement: Histograms

Table 3.2.4. Emotional school engagement: Factor structure

	Results of exploratory factor analysis			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
No of factors with eigenvalue >1	1	1	1	1
Total variance explained by factor 1, %	39.74	47.49	44.67	46.38
No of items for factor 1	4	4	4	4
Mix – max factor loadings	0.51 - 0.73	0.52 - 0.78	0.51 - 0.73	0.60 - 0.74

Note. Principal axis factoring is applied to evaluate factor structure of a scale.

Table 3.2.5. Emotional engagement: Construct validity and internal consistency

Correlates	Emotional school engagement			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
Mathematics achievement	0.083**	0.044	0.117**	0.091**
Reading achievement	0.096**	0.111**	0.132**	0.089**
Academic value	0.174**	0.314**	0.360**	0.223**
Academic self-concept	0.229**	0.371**	0.329**	0.359**
Victimization in bullying	-0.303**	-0.326**	-0.312**	-0.310**
Autonomy support	0.293**	0.410**	0.406**	0.351**
Competence support	0.301**	0.395**	0.408**	0.329**
Relatedness support	0.328**	0.394**	0.418**	0.368**
Parents academic support	0.276**	0.291**	-	-
Communication with parents	0.302**	0.303**	0.311**	0.324**
Cronbach's alpha	0.72	0.78	0.76	0.77

Note. Pearson's r correlation coefficients are presented in the table. ** - Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level, * - Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

3.3 Academic task value

3.3.1 Theoretical conceptualization of the construct

Academic task value comes from expectancy-value theory (Eccles et al., 1983; Wigfield & Eccles, 2000), which postulates that students' achievement related choices (decisions and behaviours) could be explained by their perceived value of academic tasks and beliefs about expectations for success. Academic task value is a motivational construct and together with other aspects of academic motivational processes, such as academic self-concept and emotional engagement, could be considered the most proximal psychological determinants of engagement in academic activities as well as academic performance (e.g., Eccles & Wigfield, 2020; Fredricks, Blumenfeld, & Paris, 2004; Vu et al., 2021; Wang & Eccles, 2011).

The value that a student sees in academic tasks or learning in general reflects a subjective answer to the question "Do I want to succeed in this task (learning at school)?" (Eccles, Wigfield, Midgley, Reuman, Iver, & Feldlaufer, 1993). The overall value attributed to academic activities depends on a number of characteristics of these activities, but also on the broader needs, values, goals and past experiences of a student (Eccles & Wigfield, 1995).

Task value is conceptualized as a motivational construct, which is composed of four characteristics: intrinsic value - how much the individual is interested in and enjoys doing the task, attainment value - the importance of doing well on a task or activity, utility value - the usefulness of the task for achieving future goals and cost value - the negative aspects of engaging in a task, e.g., performance anxiety, fear of failure, time consumption (Eccles et al., 1983, Eccles & Wigfield, 2020).

Students with high academic task value see academic activities as interesting, satisfying, important, instrumental for achieving their longer-term goals, and requiring relatively low investment or sacrifice to succeed. Subjective task value is very strong predictor of persistence, not to give up with learning (Eccles & Wigfield, 2020, Wigfield & Eccles, 2002, Wigfield & Eccles, 2000).

As children develop and mature, task value also becomes more conscious, sophisticated. Research shows that task value perceptions could change over time with most common pattern of decline across school years and different subjects (for example the expected value for math and reading domain declines, but not for sports). (see Wigfield, Eccles, 2000, Eccles, Wigfield, 2020, Liem, 2008).

In order to enhance students' positive perception of task value, there were conducted numerous of intervention research. From intervention perspective, special attention could be placed on utility value component. This component captures some extrinsic reasons for task engagement (for example students participate in activities not because they enjoy, but because they want to be with friends, because of parents' pressure or have other interests), so it could be considered as most malleable of the task value components and it could most likely to change through interventions. Utility-value interventions positively influence students interest and performance and also other

value components, strengthen students' willingness to take longer courses, improve retention and even could lead to reduction of social-class achievement gap (Harackiewicz, et. al. 2014, 2016).

3.3.2 Operationalization of the construct in NSSA data

The operationalization of academic value in NSSA data is in line with the conceptualization of the phenomenon as a unidimensional construct covering such value aspects as importance, willingness, responsibility for learning, utility of learning in general. Respondents were asked to express their agreement to such value aspects as:

- It is important for you to study well;
- You study willingly;
- You feel responsible for your own learning;
- You know what is important for you to learn;
- It is important for you to understand the learning objectives of the subject.

Each item was assessed on a 4-point ratio scale: 1- *completely disagree*, 2- *disagree*, 3- *agree*, 4- *completely agree*. The total score for the scale is calculated by averaging the responses for five items. The mean score represents the level of student's academic value. Higher scores indicate higher academic value. The same items and identical response scale were used to assess academic value across different rounds of NSSA (2012-2016) (see table 3.3.1).

3.3.3 Descriptive statistics

Descriptives for the scale are presented in tables 3.3.2 and 3.3.3. Mean scores are between 3.0 and 3.3, when the maximum values are 4. Median scores are 3 (except in 2016, median score is 3.2), indicating that half of participants indicated that their academic value is higher than that value of 3.

Values of skewness are negative (between -0.87 and -0.16) across different rounds of NSSA indicating that data are a little skewed to the left side. Values of kurtosis are between 1.50 and 2.73.

Individual differences are the main source of variance in academic value. Differences between schools account for only 2.4 % to 4.3 % of variance in emotional engagement in 2012 – 2015. Differences between schools were not observed in year 2016 (see ICC scores in table 3.3.2).

3.3.4 Scale validity in NSSA data

Structural validity. The unidimensional nature of the scale was supported by the findings from exploratory factor analysis (principal axis factoring) for the five academic value items (see table 3.3.4). Across all four datasets, a single factor with eigenvalue > 1 was identified. The total variance explained by the single factor ranged

from 52.32 % to 62.79 %. All item loadings were above the common cut-off point of 0.40 in all datasets.

Convergent/ divergent validity. The findings indicated from moderate to strong positive correlations between academic task value and teaching characteristics: autonomy support, competence support and relatedness support (between 0.22 and 0.57). Strong positive correlations are observed between academic task value and academic self-concept (between 0.67 and 0.78), from week to moderate positive correlation – between academic task value and emotional school engagement (between 0.17 and 0.36). Correlation between academic task value and victimization in bullying are zero to weak negative (between -0.14 and -0.032). Moderate positive correlations are observed between academic task value and relationships with parents (between 0.22 and 0.38). Correlations between academic task value and academic achievements are from weak to moderate positive - between 0.17 and 0.23 (see table 3.3.5).

Internal consistency. Acceptable internal consistency was observed for the scale across all rounds of NSSA, Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.77 to 0.85.

Table 3.3.1. Academic task value: Scale structure and syntax

Intro: Do you agree with these statements:			
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
A1a/It is important for you to study well/ <i>Tau yra svarbu gerai mokytis</i>	A1a/It is important for you to study well/ <i>Tau yra svarbu gerai mokytis</i>	A1a/It is important for you to study well/ <i>Tau yra svarbu gerai mokytis</i>	A1a/It is important for you to study well/ <i>Tau yra svarbu gerai mokytis</i>
A1b/You study willingly/ Mokaisi noriai			
A1c/Feel responsible for your own learning/ <i>Jautiesi atsakingas už savo mokymąsi</i>	A1c/Feel responsible for your own learning/ <i>Jautiesi atsakingas už savo mokymąsi</i>	A1c/Feel responsible for your own learning/ <i>Jautiesi atsakingas už savo mokymąsi</i>	A1c/Feel responsible for your own learning/ <i>Jautiesi atsakingas už savo mokymąsi</i>
A3a/You know what is important for you to learn/ <i>Žinai, ko Tau svarbu išmokti</i>	A3a/You know what is important for you to learn/ <i>Žinai, ko Tau svarbu išmokti</i>	A3a/You know what is important for you to learn/ <i>Žinai, ko Tau svarbu išmokti</i>	A3a/You know what is important for you to learn/ <i>Žinai, ko Tau svarbu išmokti</i>
A3b/It is important for you to understand the learning objectives of the subject/ <i>Tau svarbu suprasti dalyko mokymosi tikslus</i>	A3b/It is important for you to understand the learning objectives of the subject/ <i>Tau svarbu suprasti dalyko mokymosi tikslus</i>	A3b/It is important for you to understand the learning objectives of the subject/ <i>Tau svarbu suprasti dalyko mokymosi tikslus</i>	A3b/It is important for you to understand the learning objectives of the subject/ <i>Tau svarbu suprasti dalyko mokymosi tikslus</i>
Response scale:		5. <i>Completely disagree</i>	
		6. <i>Disagree</i>	
		7. <i>Agree</i>	
		8. <i>Completely agree</i>	
Missings:		98, 99	
Scale total			
AcVAL=MEAN(A1a, A1b, A1c, A3a, A3b).			

Table 3.3.2. Academic task value: Scale descriptives

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	992	830	431	430
Missing	3487	2933	3051	2280
Min - Max	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4
Mean (SD)	3.14 (0.45)	3.01 (0.49)	3.15 (0.49)	3.26 (0.52)
Median	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.2
Skewness (st.error)	-0.16 (0.08)	-0.30 (0.09)	-0.37 (0.12)	-0.87 (0.12)
Kurtosis (st.error)	1.19 (0.16)	1.35 (0.17)	1.50 (0.24)	2.73 (0.24)
ICC (school)	0.024	0.037	0.043	_*

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in academic value accounted by school-level differences.

*- no differences between schools are observed.

Table 3.3.3. Academic task value: Histograms

Table 3.3.4. Academic task value: Factor structure

	Results of exploratory factor analysis			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
No of factors with eigenvalue >1	1	1	1	1
Total variance explained by factor 1, %	52.32	57.92	54.97	62.79
No of items for factor 1	5	5	5	5
Mix – max factor loadings	0.54 - 0.71	0.63 - 0.73	0.59 - 0.74	0.60 - 0.79

Note. Principal axis factoring is applied to evaluate factor structure of a scale.

Table 3.3.5. Academic task value: Construct validity and internal consistency

Correlates	Academic task value			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
Mathematics achievement	0.187**	0.219**	0.165**	0.199**
Reading achievement	0.181**	0.214**	0.229**	0.114*
Academic self-concept	0.674**	0.711**	0.683**	0.776**
Emotional engagement	0.174**	0.314**	0.360**	0.223**
Victimization in bullying	-0.032	-0.144**	-0.092	-0.067
Autonomy support	0.307**	0.422**	0.341**	0.543**
Competence support	0.292**	0.382**	0.385**	0.510**
Relatedness support	0.280**	0.375**	0.334**	0.570**
Parents academic support	0.223**	0.378**	-	-
Communication with parents	0.234**	0.377**	0.301**	0.265**
Cronbach's alpha	0.77	0.82	0.79	0.85

Note. Pearson's r correlation coefficients are presented in the table. ** - Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level, * - Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

3.4 Victimization in bullying

3.4.1 Theoretical conceptualization of the construct

In developmental research on children and adolescents bullying is discussed in a broader context of peer victimization (Hong & Espelage, 2012). Based on a classical definition by Olweus (1993), victimization in bullying is being exposed to repeated acts over time, that are intended to cause physical or psychological discomfort or injury, and are carried out by a person or group in a position of more power. Victimization in bullying can occur directly (e.g., experiencing pushing, shoving, hitting, kicking, or restraint from peers) or indirectly (e.g., being teased, taunted, threatened, called names, or smeared) (Olweus, 1993).

Poverty is considered a risk factor for bullying victimization (Hong & Espelage, 2012). Youth from low-income families are more likely to be exposed to peer violence in school (Carlson, 2006). With regard to academic achievement, both children with highest levels of school achievement and those with learning difficulties are at risk of experiencing bullying from peers at school (Hong & Espelage, 2012). Bullying victimization can have long-term negative consequences for victims and is associated with severe levels of intra- and interpersonal difficulties, such as anxiety, withdrawal, depressive tendencies, poor self-esteem, somatization, low social competence, and impaired school functioning (Goldbaum, Craig, Pepler, & Connolly, 2003; Hawker, & Boulton, 2000; Olweus, 1994).

Different forms of victimization in traditional bullying at school are commonly included in bullying assessment: verbal (name calling), threatening (intimidation), physical (including physical hurt, but also property damage or stealing), relational (e.g., exclusion from friendships), and social (lies, rumors, etc.) (Shaw et al., 2013). Some authors discuss the need to include electronic forms of bullying (or cyberbullying) victimization, since a substantial share of bullying among children and adolescents happens in cyber spaces or by the means of digital devices (Ybarra, Diener-West, & Leaf, 2007). However, others argue that it is not necessary to distinguish between traditional and electronic forms of bullying since it may be difficult for young people to report on these behaviors separately (Shaw et al., 2013).

Different forms of victimization in bullying are considered to make up one broader construct of victimization in bullying (Shaw et al., 2013). Thus, a multi-item scale measuring victimization in bullying is commonly used, with composite scores, for example, mean scores, indicating the level of bullying victimization. A multi-item scale of bullying victimization is considered to have greater sensitivity and variability than a binary outcome and reflect the continuous nature of the latent victimization variable (Shaw et al., 2013).

3.4.2 Operationalization of the construct in NSSA data

The operationalization of victimization in bullying in NSSA data is in line with the conceptualization of the phenomenon as a unidimensional construct covering several forms of peer victimization, including verbal, threatening, physical, relational, and

social victimization. The scale used to assess the level of victimization asks a respondent whether they face five forms of behaviors from other students in their school „Do other students in your school“:

- Call you names, mock you
- Make you feel uncomfortable
- Send you offensive messages (by phone or otherwise), insult, threaten you, and so on
- Try to prevent your friends from getting along with you
- Take your things or money

Each item was assessed on a 4-point ratio scale: 1- *never/ very rarely*, 2-*sometimes*, 3-*often*, 4-*very often*. Notably, the measure does not specify a period of reference for reporting victimization (as often done in other instruments assessing the rates of bullying, e.g., Shaw et al., 2013). In addition, the categories on the scale refer to subjective understanding of a respondent regarding the frequency of their encounters with bullying behaviors rather than more standardized responses on the actual frequencies (e.g., once a week, several times a week, etc., Shaw et al., 2013).

The total score for the scale is calculated by averaging the responses for all five items (as in Shaw et al., 2013). The mean score represents a sum of the frequency and the number of different ways in which a student was bullied. Higher scores indicate greater exposure to bullying. The same items and identical response scale was used to assess victimization in bullying across different rounds of NSSA (2012-2016) (see table 3.4.1).

3.4.3 Descriptive statistics

Descriptives for the scale are presented in tables 3.4.2 and 3.4.3. The distribution of scores is skewed towards the lower end of the scale and has a peak at the lowest point on the scale (i.e., either no or very rare instances of victimization in bullying). Observed pattern is consistent across all rounds of NSSA. It is also similar to the ones reported in previous studies (e.g., Erentaitė, Žukauskienė, & Bergman, 2012; Shaw et al., 2013). Mean scores are close to the minimum value of 1. In all rounds of the study around half of the students have mean scores of 1 (experience no or very rare victimization).

Generally, the distribution of the scale with inflated scores at the lowest point of the scale indicates potential relevance of a categorical scale instead of interval scale to assess the level of bullying victimization. The functionality of the cut-off points are discussed in the literature on bullying (e.g., Solberg & Olweus, 2003), however, the differences in the response scales have to be taken into account (pre-specified vs subjective judgements) when considering recommended cut-offs. A more data-driven approach would be to use cluster analyses with the five victimization items to identify the actual patterns of intensity and forms of bullying victimization, as suggested in previous studies by Erentaitė et al. (2012) or Gradinger, Strohmeier, & Spiel (2009).

Individual differences are the main source of variance in bullying victimization. Differences between schools account for 3.1% to 7.0 % of variance in bullying victimization (see ICC scores in table 3.4.2).

3.4.4 Scale validity in NSSA data

Structural validity. The unidimensional nature of the scale was supported by the findings from exploratory factor analysis (principal axis factoring) for the five victimization items (see table 3.4.4). Across all four datasets, a single factor with eigenvalue > 1 was identified. The total variance explained by the single factor ranged from 55.5 % to 60 %. All item loadings were above the common cut-off point of 0.40 in all datasets.

Convergent/ divergent validity. We assessed the patterns of convergence and divergence of scores on bullying victimization with other measures of emotional and relational functioning. Specifically, we expected a negative correlation of victimization in bullying with emotional school engagement, relatedness support from teachers, as well as communication with parents. The findings indicated weak to moderate associations in the expected direction (see table 3.4.5) in support for the construct validity of victimization in bullying scale.

Internal consistency. High internal consistency was observed for the scale across all rounds of NSSA, Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.79 to 0.82.

Table 3.4.1. Victimization in bullying: Scale structure and syntax

Intro: Do other students in your school:				
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)	
B25a/ Call you names, mock you	B26a/ Call you names, mock you	B23a/ Call you names, mock you	B23a/ Call you names, mock you	
B25b/ Make you feel uncomfortable	B26b/ Make you feel uncomfortable	B23b/ Make you feel uncomfortable	B23b/ Make you feel uncomfortable	
B25c/ Send you offensive messages (by phone or otherwise), insult, threaten you, and so on	B26c/ Send you offensive messages (by phone or otherwise), insult, threaten you, and so on	B23c/ Send you offensive messages (by phone or otherwise), insult, threaten you, and so on	B23c/ Send you offensive messages (by phone or otherwise), insult, threaten you, and so on	
B25d/ Try to prevent your friends from getting along with you	B26d/ Try to prevent your friends from getting along with you	B23d/ Try to prevent your friends from getting along with you	B23d/ Try to prevent your friends from getting along with you	
B25e/ Take your things or money	B26e/ Take your things or money	B23e/ Take your things or money	B23e/ Take your things or money	
Response scale:		1- <i>Never/ very rarely</i>		
		2- <i>Sometimes</i>		
		3- <i>Often</i>		
		4- <i>Very often</i>		
Missings:		98, 99		
Scale total				
BULL = MEAN(B25a, B25b, B25c, B25d, B25e)		BULL = MEAN(B26a, B26b, B26c, B26d, B26e)		BULL = MEAN(B23a, B23b, B23c, B23d, B23e)

Table 3.4.2. Victimization in bullying: Scale descriptives

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	4451	3735	3435	2687
Missing	28	28	47	23
Min - Max	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4
Mean (SD)	1.28 (0.44)	1.29 (0.47)	1.26 (0.43)	1.31 (0.46)

Median	1.20	1.00	1.00	1.20
Skewness (st.error)	2.70 (0.04)	2.58 (0.04)	2.96 (0.04)	2.22 (0.05)
Kurtosis (st.error)	9.65 (0.07)	8.34 (0.08)	11.59 (0.08)	6.14 (0.09)
% of no or very rare victimization (score = 1)	48.6	51.7	51.1	46.6
ICC (school)	0.046	0.048	0.031	0.07

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in bullying victimization accounted by school-level differences.

Table 3.4.3. Victimization in bullying: Histograms

Table 3.4.4. Victimization in bullying: Factor structure

	Results of exploratory factor analysis			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
No of factors with eigenvalue >1	1	1	1	1
Total variance explained by factor 1, %	58.17	59.84	56.91	55.50
No of items for factor 1	5	5	5	5
Mix – max factor loadings	0.54 - 0.79	0.56 - 0.79	0.48 - 0.75	0.49 - 0.81

Note. Principal axis factoring is applied to evaluate factor structure of a scale.

Table 3.4.5. Victimization in bullying: Construct validity and internal consistency

Correlates	Victimization in bullying			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
Emotional engagement	-0.303**	-0.326**	-0.312**	-0.310**
Relatedness support	-0.081*	-0.134**	-0.109*	-0.204**
Communication with parents	-0.138**	-0.182**	-0.182**	-0.165**
Cronbach's alpha	0.81	0.82	0.80	0.79

Note. Pearson's r correlation coefficients are presented in the table. All correlations are significant at the .001 level

4. ASSESSING PERCEIVED TEACHING CHARACTERISTICS: SUPPORT FOR AUTONOMY, COMPETENCE, AND RELATEDNESS

4.1 Theoretical conceptualization of the constructs

Self-determination theory postulates that autonomy, competence, and relatedness are psychological needs relevant to all humans (Ryan & Deci, 2000). The study of Ryan & Powelson (1991) revealed that autonomy, competence, and relatedness, the three psychological needs, synergistically and interactively promote development and behaviour, and how the educational context influences the motivation driven by these needs. There are many desires, needs and purposes that influence the intrinsic direction of psychological development, but autonomy, competence and relatedness reveal what is most important (Ryan & Powelson, 1991).

The term *autonomy* refers to the regulation of a person's experience and behaviour, as well as the initiation of action and direction. By acting autonomously, a person experiences the self to be an agent of one's behaviour (Ryan & Powelson, 1991). The need for autonomy refers to the experience of behaviour as volitional and reflectively self-endorsed (Niemic & Ryan, 2009). *Competence* is related to the sense of achievement and outcome that results from exploiting one's abilities in an optimally challenging environment. The important thing is that competency needs operate without external factors, that is, they are reinforced in contexts that provide autonomy (Ryan and Powelson, 1991). The need for competence means the experience of effective behaviour. Importantly, in order to maintain intrinsic motivation, it is necessary to meet the needs for autonomy and competence. Students who feel competent but not autonomous will not maintain intrinsic motivation to learn. To date, many of experimental studies have confirmed self-determination theory postulate that autonomy and competence are prerequisites for maintaining intrinsic motivation (Niemic and Ryan, 2009). Self-determination theory postulates that perceived competence will not lead to greater well-being unless the behaviour is perceived as self-inflicted, as a personal decision, that is, autonomous (Levesque, Zuehlke, Stanek, & Ryan, 2004). The pursuit of personal competence is most often manifested in conditions that support autonomy (Niemic & Ryan, 2009). The individual must feel competent to experience greater well-being and at the same time feel autonomous in choosing actions (Fisher, 1978; Ryan1982). *Relatedness* is about emotional and personal connections between individuals. It reflects a person's desire to connect, support, and interact with others. Relatedness means more than just connection. Relatedness refers to the experience of connecting with others in a way that promotes the well-being and mutual self-cohesion in all involved. Relatedness needs are not opposed to either competence or autonomy (Ryan, 1991), and in fact, a person often feels most connected to those who respond to his or her autonomous expressions (Ryan and Powelson, 1991).

Under favourable conditions for to autonomy, competence, and relatedness to unfold, people are likely to express their innate tendency to learn, improve and develop. People are motivated and engaged in areas where their basic psychological needs may be met periodically. This basic assumption of the organism's approach is crucial in

translating it into the school context and applying it in the teaching process (Vansteenkiste, Niemiec, Soenens, 2010; Niemiec & Ryan, 2009; Deci & Ryan, 2000; Reeve, Bolt, & Cai, 1999; Reeve, 1998). The needs expressed by students, which can lead to their involvement in schooling, are largely interpersonal in nature. In the context of education and tasks where students experience support for their autonomy, feel connected to and are supported by significant others, they are likely to be highly motivated. Conversely, in contexts that are controlling and where students feel disconnected, unrelated to significant others, students are likely to feel alienated and disengaged. The needs for autonomy and relatedness affect the educational process and the motivation of students to engage in school activities (Levesque, Zuehlke, Stanek, & Ryan, 2004; Ryan and Powelson, 1991).

An environment that supports autonomy is one that allows for self-determination and choice when there are almost no goals, demands, judgments, and pressures imposed. Autonomy-supportive context offers more positive, non-judgmental informative feedback and is sensitive to the other person's perspective (Deci and Ryan, 1985, 2000; Reeve, 1998; Reeve, Bolt, & Cai, 1999; Ryan and Deci, 2000). Research has found that teachers who support autonomy increase their students' self-motivation and desire for challenges (Deci & Ryan, 2000; Reeve, 1998; Reeve, Bolt, & Cai, 1999; Ryan & Deci, 2000).

Teachers differ in their propensity to control students or maintain their independence; their 'operating styles range from highly controlled to highly autonomy supportive. Relatively controlling teachers set an agenda for students to follow, and these teachers use instructions and external motivators to encourage students to follow that agenda. This approach is controlling because the teacher makes an effort to control the goals and behaviours of the students to achieve the set goal. Relatively autonomy-supportive teachers encourage students to set and pursue their own agendas. Such teachers encourage, support students' initiatives and intrinsic motivation. This approach supports autonomy because the goal of the teacher is to strengthen students' autonomous self-regulation (Levesque, Zuehlke, Stanek, & Ryan, 2004).

Academic achievement is higher among students whose teachers support and promote autonomy compared to students whose teachers are controlling. Research has revealed that students of teachers who support autonomy also have a better understanding of concepts and a lower dropout rate (Vansteenkiste, Niemiec, Soenens, 2010; Oliver et al., 2008; Reeve, Bolt, & Cai, 1999). Research has found that teachers who support autonomy increase their students' autonomous motivation and desire for challenges (Levesque, Zuehlke, Stanek, & Ryan, 2004). The researchers found that teachers who claimed to support autonomy actually taught in ways that nurture, encourage, and support student autonomy. These teachers listened more, gave less instruction, verbalize fewer directives, asked more about what the student wanted or intended to do, answered more of the questions generated by the students, and offered more possible alternatives (Reeve, Bolt, & Cai, 1999; Reeve, 1998).

Strategies to increase autonomy include encouraging and teaching students to choose learning activities, listening to why such choices have been made, acknowledging students' feelings about the topics they are studying, and avoiding pressure and control (Niemiec & Ryan, 2009). Students' competence can be developed applying learning activities that are optimally complex. This allows students to expand and

grow their academic abilities. Competence development strategies or support include teacher and students discussions of how to complete the task, advice on how to make it easier to learn a difficult topic, an explanation of what difficulties we may face in completing the task, and what to do next. Competence development strategies also include timely, comprehensive feedback on the tasks they perform. Students will be involved and value only those activities that they will understand and be able to master. Therefore, targeted and timely feedback would show students their appropriate outcomes, provide reinforcement, and provide guidelines for improvement as a task to perform better (Niemic & Ryan, 2009; Reeve, Bolt, & Cai, 1999; Reeve, 1998; Ryan & Powelson, 1991). Competence development strategies include the provision of impact-based rather than norm-based assessment, feedback, and optimally challenging tasks. Strategies for strengthening or support relatedness include conveying warmth, care, and respect to students, encouraging students to be self-confident, focused and caring about learning, advising on how to organize learning to achieve better results (Niemic & Ryan, 2009; Reeve, Bolt, & Cai, 1999; Reeve, 1998). Autonomy and relatedness have been shown to be essential for learning. Therefore, facilitative environments are those that create and sustain interpersonal engagement and self-reliance (Ryan & Powelson, 1991). Numerous studies confirm the Self-determination theory postulate that meeting students' basic psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness is critical to mastering academic motivation. Research has confirmed that meeting all three basic psychological needs was associated with greater learning experiences and greater academic achievement. An environment that maintains satisfaction with autonomy, competence, and relatedness, students are more motivated and more likely to perform less interesting tasks and appreciate academic performance. With a greater desire, learners demonstrate higher quality learning outcomes, better well-being and greater value in the services provided by the school. Recognizing the importance of an interpersonal atmosphere between teachers and students in fostering intrinsic motivation to learn can help reorient educators' goals and practices to focus less on cognitive standards and focus more on increasing student interest and engagement in learning (Vansteenkiste, Niemic, Soenens, 2010; Ryan & Powelson, 1991).

4.2 Operationalization, descriptives and validity of the constructs in NSSA data

Similar to previous studies (e.g. Van den Berghe, Cardon, Tallir, Kirk & Haerens, 2016, Abós, Javier, Martín-Albo, Julián, & García-González, 2018) and in aligned with a developmental motivational perspective (Connell & Wellborn, 1991; Deci & Ryan, 1985; Eccles & Midgley, 1989, Roeser, Eccles, & Sameroff, 1998), the three dimensions of teaching behavior (autonomy support, competence support and relatedness support) are presented in the measure.

4.2.1 Autonomy support

Autonomy support was measured by three items reflecting students' perspective on teachers' provision of rationales and instruction variability that stimulate students' feeling that they are the causal agents of their learning (Deci, Ryan, 2000). Respondents were asked to express their agreement to such support aspects as:

- Teachers make sure we are interested in learning;
- Teachers help you to understand what you are learning and why;
- Teachers teach us to learn in a variety of ways.

Each item was assessed on a 4-point ratio scale: 1- *completely disagree*, 2- *disagree*, 3- *agree*, 4- *completely agree*. The total score for the scale is calculated by averaging the responses for three items. The mean score represents the level of student's autonomy support. Higher scores indicate higher autonomy support. The same items and identical response scale were used to assess autonomy support concept across different rounds of NSSA (2012-2016) (see table 4.2.1.1).

Descriptive statistics. Descriptives for the scale are presented in tables 4.2.1.2 and 4.2.1.3. Mean scores are between 2.8 and 3.0, when the maximum values are 4. Median scores are 3.0, indicating that half of participants indicated that their autonomy support is higher than value of 3.0.

Values of skewness are negative (between -0.70 and -0.30) across different rounds of NSSA indicating that data are a little skewed to the left side. Values of kurtosis are between 0.26 and 1.29. Overall, a normal distribution of this scale data could be assumed.

Individual differences are the main source of variance in autonomy support. Differences between schools account for 4.1% to 12.8 % of variance in autonomy support (see ICC scores in table 4.2.1.2).

Scale validity in NSSA data: Structural validity. The unidimensional nature of the scale was supported by the findings from exploratory factor analysis (principal axis factoring) for the three autonomy support items (see table 4.2.1.4). Across all four datasets, a single factor with eigenvalue > 1 was identified. The total variance explained by the single factor ranged from 69.76 % to 71.15 %. All item loadings were above the common cut-off point of 0.40 in all datasets.

Convergent/ divergent validity. The findings indicated strong positive correlations between autonomy support and another teaching characteristics: competence support and relatedness support (between 0.77 and 0.84). From moderate to strong positive correlation are observed between autonomy support and such students characteristics as: academics self-concept, emotional school engagement and academic task value (between 0.29 and 0.54). Correlation between autonomy support and victimization in bullying are zero to weak negative (between -0.15 and -0.03). From weak to moderate positive correlations are observed between autonomy support and relationships with parents (between 0.17 and 0.29). Correlations between autonomy support and academic achievements in most cases are zero to weak negative (between -0.11 and -0.02) (see table 4.2.1.5).

Internal consistency. Acceptable internal consistency was observed for the scale across all rounds of NSSA, Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.76 to 0.79.

Table 4.2.1.1. Autonomy support: Scale structure and syntax

Intro: Do you agree with these statements:			
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
K1a/Teachers make sure we are interested in learning/ <i>Mokytojai pasirūpina, kad mums būtų įdomu mokytis</i>	K1a/Teachers make sure we are interested in learning/ <i>Mokytojai pasirūpina, kad mums būtų įdomu mokytis</i>	K1a/Teachers make sure we are interested in learning/ <i>Mokytojai pasirūpina, kad mums būtų įdomu mokytis</i>	K1a/Teachers make sure we are interested in learning/ <i>Mokytojai pasirūpina, kad mums būtų įdomu mokytis</i>
K3a/Teachers help you understand what you are learning and why/ <i>Mokytojai Tau padeda suprasti, ko ir kodėl mokaisi</i>	K3a/Teachers help you understand what you are learning and why/ <i>Mokytojai Tau padeda suprasti, ko ir kodėl mokaisi</i>	K3a/Teachers help you understand what you are learning and why/ <i>Mokytojai Tau padeda suprasti, ko ir kodėl mokaisi</i>	K3a/Teachers help you understand what you are learning and why/ <i>Mokytojai Tau padeda suprasti, ko ir kodėl mokaisi</i>
K5a/Teachers teach us to learn in a variety of ways/ <i>Mokytojai mus moko mokytis įvairiais būdais</i>	K5a/Teachers teach us to learn in a variety of ways/ <i>Mokytojai mus moko mokytis įvairiais būdais</i>	K5a/Teachers teach us to learn in a variety of ways/ <i>Mokytojai mus moko mokytis įvairiais būdais</i>	K5a/Teachers teach us to learn in a variety of ways/ <i>Mokytojai mus moko mokytis įvairiais būdais</i>
Response scale:		1. <i>Completely disagree</i>	
		2. <i>Disagree</i>	
		3. <i>Agree</i>	
		4. <i>Completely agree</i>	
		Missings: 98, 99	

Scale total

AuSUPP=MEAN(K1a, K3a, K5a)

AuSUPP=MEAN(K1a, K3a, K5a)

AuSUPP=MEAN(K1a, K3a, K5a)

AuSUPP=MEAN(K1a, K3a, K5a)

Table 4.2.1.2. Autonomy support: Scale descriptives

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	988	827	428	430
Missing	3491	2936	3054	2280
Min - Max	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4
Mean (SD)	2.85 (0.60)	2.75 (0.61)	2.92 (0.63)	3.00 (0.63)
Median	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Skewness (st.error)	-0.35 (0.08)	-0.47 (0.09)	-0.30 (0.19)	-0.70 (0.12)
Kurtosis (st.error)	0.66 (0.16)	0.77 (0.17)	0.26 (0.24)	1.29 (0.24)
ICC (school)	0.104	0.054	0.128	0.041

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in autonomy support accounted by school-level differences.

Table 4.2.1.3. Autonomy support: Histograms

Table 4.2.1.4. Autonomy support: Factor structure

	Results of exploratory factor analysis			
	2012	2014	2015	2016

No of factors with eigenvalue >1	1	1	1	1
Total variance explained by factor 10. %	67.97	69.25	71.15	69.76
No of items for factor 1	3	3	3	3
Mix – max factor loadings	0.71 – 0.73	0.70 – 0.76	0.72 – 0.81	0.69 – 0.81

Note. Principal axis factoring is applied to evaluate factor structure of a scale.

Table 4.2.1.5. Autonomy support: Construct validity and internal consistency

Correlates	Autonomy support			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
Mathematics achievement	-0.051	-0.016	-0.105*	0.037
Reading achievement	-0.099**	-0.072	-0.086	-0.082
Academic value	0.307**	0.422**	0.341**	0.543**
Academic self-concept	0.307**	0.455**	0.423**	0.568**
Emotional engagement	0.293**	0.410**	0.406**	0.351**
Victimization in bullying	-0.025	-0.146**	-0.076	-0.153**
Competence support	0.776**	0.789**	0.799**	0.815**
Relatedness support	0.771**	0.801**	0.806**	0.835**
Parental academic support	0.202**	0.290**	-	-
Communication with parents	0.170**	0.243**	0.323**	0.214**
Cronbach's alpha	0.76	0.78	0.79	0.78

Note. Pearson's r correlation coefficients are presented in the table. ** - Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. * - Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

4.2.2 Competence support

Competence support was assessed by seven items capturing different teaching practices that allow to create a well-structured studying environment. **Competence support** strengthens the students' feeling that they could effectively achieve learning goals (Skinner, Belmont, 1993). Respondents were asked to express their agreement to such support aspects as:

- We discuss with teachers how we will complete one task or another, how long it will take, and so on;
- Teachers advise us on how to make it easier to learn one thing or another;
- Teachers explain what difficulties we may face in completing the task and what should be done then;
- Together with teachers, we try out different ways that help us track our learning progress;
- Teachers advise and monitor that we get the job done on time;
- In difficult lessons, teachers offer a few minutes of rest (rest breaks);
- Teachers give you the help you need to keep learning time in vain.

Each item was assessed on a 4-point ratio scale: 1- *completely disagree*, 2- *disagree*, 3- *agree*, 4- *completely agree*. The total score for the scale is calculated by averaging the responses for seven items. The mean score represents the level of student's competence support. Higher scores indicate higher competence support. The same items and identical response scale were used to assess competence support concept across different rounds of NSSA (2012-2016) (see table 4.2.2.1).

Descriptive statistics. Descriptives for the scale are presented in tables 4.2.2.2 and 4.2.2.3. Mean scores are between 2.8 and 3.1, when the maximum values are 4. Median scores are 2.9 (except in 2016, median score is 3.0) indicating that half of participants indicated that their competence support is higher than value of 3.0.

Values of skewness are negative (between -0.53 and -0.17) across different rounds of NSSA indicating that data are a little skewed to the left side. Values of kurtosis are between 1.02 and 1.78.

Individual differences are the main source of variance in competence support. Differences between schools account for 5.5% to 11.2 % of variance in competence support (see ICC scores in table 4.2.2.2).

Structural validity. The unidimensional nature of the scale was supported by the findings from exploratory factor analysis (principal axis factoring) for the seven competence support items (see table 4.2.2.4). Across all four datasets, a single factor with eigenvalue > 1 was identified. The total variance explained by the single factor ranged from 48.48 % to 58.90 %. All item loadings were above the common cut-off point of 0.40 in all datasets.

Convergent/ divergent validity. The findings indicated strong positive correlations between competence support and other teaching characteristics: autonomy support and relatedness support (between 0.78 and 0.87). From moderate to strong positive

correlation are observed between competence support and such students characteristics as: academics self-concept, emotional school engagement and academic task value (between 0.29 and 0.51). Correlation between competence support and victimization in bullying are weak negative (between -0.13 and -0.1). From weak to moderate positive correlations are observed between competence support and relationships with parents (between 0.19 and 0.32). Correlations between competence support and academic achievements are zero to weak negative (between -0.09 and 0.05) (see table 4.2.2.5).

Internal consistency. Acceptable internal consistency was observed for the scale across all rounds of NSSA, Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.82 to 0.88.

Table 4.2.2.1. Competence support: Scale structure and syntax

Intro: Do you agree with these statements:			
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
K3b/We discuss with teachers how we will complete one task or another, how long it will take, and so on/ <i>Su mokytojais aptariame, kaip atliksime vieną ar kitą užduotį, kiek tam reikės laiko ir pan.</i>	K3b/We discuss with teachers how we will complete one task or another, how long it will take, and so on/ <i>Su mokytojais aptariame, kaip atliksime vieną ar kitą užduotį, kiek tam reikės laiko ir pan.</i>	K3b/We discuss with teachers how we will complete one task or another, how long it will take, and so on/ <i>Su mokytojais aptariame, kaip atliksime vieną ar kitą užduotį, kiek tam reikės laiko ir pan.</i>	K3b/We discuss with teachers how we will complete one task or another, how long it will take, and so on/ <i>Su mokytojais aptariame, kaip atliksime vieną ar kitą užduotį, kiek tam reikės laiko ir pan.</i>
K5b/Teachers advise us on how to make it easier to learn one thing or another/ <i>Mokytojai mums pataria, kaip lengviau būtų išmokti vieną ar kitą dalyką</i>	K5b/Teachers advise us on how to make it easier to learn one thing or another/ <i>Mokytojai mums pataria, kaip lengviau būtų išmokti vieną ar kitą dalyką</i>	K5b/Teachers advise us on how to make it easier to learn one thing or another/ <i>Mokytojai mums pataria, kaip lengviau būtų išmokti vieną ar kitą dalyką</i>	K5b/Teachers advise us on how to make it easier to learn one thing or another/ <i>Mokytojai mums pataria, kaip lengviau būtų išmokti vieną ar kitą dalyką</i>
K3d/Teachers explain what difficulties we may face in completing the task and what should be done then/ <i>Mokytojai paaiškina, su kokiais sunkumais galime susidurti atlikdami užduotį ir ką reikėtų tada daryti</i>	K3d/Teachers explain what difficulties we may face in completing the task and what should be done then/ <i>Mokytojai paaiškina, su kokiais sunkumais galime susidurti atlikdami užduotį ir ką reikėtų tada daryti</i>	K3d/Teachers explain what difficulties we may face in completing the task and what should be done then/ <i>Mokytojai paaiškina, su kokiais sunkumais galime susidurti atlikdami užduotį ir ką reikėtų tada daryti</i>	K3d/Teachers explain what difficulties we may face in completing the task and what should be done then/ <i>Mokytojai paaiškina, su kokiais sunkumais galime susidurti atlikdami užduotį ir ką reikėtų tada daryti</i>
K6a/Together with teachers, we try out different ways that help us track our learning progress/ <i>Kartu su mokytojais išbandome įvairius būdus, kurie padeda mums stebėti savo mokymosi pažangą</i>	K6a/Together with teachers, we try out different ways that help us track our learning progress/ <i>Kartu su mokytojais išbandome įvairius būdus, kurie padeda mums stebėti savo mokymosi pažangą</i>	K6a/Together with teachers, we try out different ways that help us track our learning progress/ <i>Kartu su mokytojais išbandome įvairius būdus, kurie padeda mums stebėti savo mokymosi pažangą</i>	K6a/Together with teachers, we try out different ways that help us track our learning progress/ <i>Kartu su mokytojais išbandome įvairius būdus, kurie padeda mums stebėti savo mokymosi pažangą</i>

Intro: Do you agree with these statements:

2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
K4a/Teachers advise and monitor that we get the job done on time/ <i>Mokytojai pataria ir stebi, kad darbą atliktume laiku</i>	K4a/Teachers advise and monitor that we get the job done on time/ <i>Mokytojai pataria ir stebi, kad darbą atliktume laiku</i>	K4a/Teachers advise and monitor that we get the job done on time/ <i>Mokytojai pataria ir stebi, kad darbą atliktume laiku</i>	K4a/Teachers advise and monitor that we get the job done on time/ <i>Mokytojai pataria ir stebi, kad darbą atliktume laiku</i>
K4b/In difficult lessons, teachers offer a few minutes of rest (rest breaks)/ <i>Pamokose atliekant sunkias užduotis mokytojai pasiūlo keletą minučių pailsėti (poilsio pertraukėlių)</i>	K4b/In difficult lessons, teachers offer a few minutes of rest (rest breaks)/ <i>Pamokose atliekant sunkias užduotis mokytojai pasiūlo keletą minučių pailsėti (poilsio pertraukėlių)</i>	K4b/In difficult lessons, teachers offer a few minutes of rest (rest breaks)/ <i>Pamokose atliekant sunkias užduotis mokytojai pasiūlo keletą minučių pailsėti (poilsio pertraukėlių)</i>	K4b/In difficult lessons, teachers offer a few minutes of rest (rest breaks)/ <i>Pamokose atliekant sunkias užduotis mokytojai pasiūlo keletą minučių pailsėti (poilsio pertraukėlių)</i>
K4d/Teachers give you the help you need to keep learning time in vain/ <i>Mokytojai suteikia Tau reikalingą pagalbą, kad neleistum mokymosi laiko veltui</i>	K4d/Teachers give you the help you need to keep learning time in vain/ <i>Mokytojai suteikia Tau reikalingą pagalbą, kad neleistum mokymosi laiko veltui</i>	K4d/Teachers give you the help you need to keep learning time in vain/ <i>Mokytojai suteikia Tau reikalingą pagalbą, kad neleistum mokymosi laiko veltui</i>	K4d/Teachers give you the help you need to keep learning time in vain/ <i>Mokytojai suteikia Tau reikalingą pagalbą, kad neleistum mokymosi laiko veltui</i>
Response scale:		1. <i>Completely disagree</i>	
		2. <i>Disagree</i>	
		3. <i>Agree</i>	
		4. <i>Completely agree</i>	
		Missings: 98, 99	

Scale total

CoSUPP=MEAN(K3b, K5b, K3d, K6a, K4a, K4b, K4d)

Table 4.2.2.2. Competence support: Scale descriptives

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	987	824	427	429
Missing	3492	2939	3055	2281
Min - Max	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4
Mean (SD)	2.84 (0.49)	2.79 (0.50)	2.89 (0.51)	3.08 (0.55)
Median	2.86	2.86	2.86	3.0
Skewness (st.error)	-0.17 (0.08)	-0.34 (0.09)	-0.45 (0.19)	-0.53 (0.12)
Kurtosis (st.error)	1.02 (0.16)	1.59 (0.17)	1.78 (0.24)	1.04 (0.24)
ICC (school)	0.061	0.055	0.112	0.061

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in competence support accounted by school-level differences.

Table 4.2.2.3. Competence support: Histograms

Table 4.2.2.4. Competence support: Factor structure

	Results of exploratory factor analysis			
	2012	2014	2015	2016

No of factors with eigenvalue >1	1	1	1	1
Total variance explained by factor 10. %	48.48	50.10	53.70	58.90
No of items for factor 1	7	7	7	7
Mix – max factor loadings	0.54 - 0.74	0.54 - 0.71	0.58 - 0.73	0.59 - 0.80

Note. Principal axis factoring is applied to evaluate factor structure of a scale

Table 4.2.2.5. Competence support: Construct validity and internal consistency

Correlates	Competence support			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
Mathematics achievement	-0.056	-0.030	-0.062	0.045
Reading achievement	-0.090**	-0.090	-0.058	-0.012
Academic value	0.292**	0.382**	0.385**	0.510**
Academic self-concept	0.296**	0.417**	0.464**	0.509**
Emotional engagement	0.301**	0.395**	0.408**	0.329**
Victimization in bullying	-0.130**	-0.123**	-0.104*	-0.125*
Autonomy support	0.776**	0.789**	0.799**	0.815**
Relatedness support	0.817**	0.820**	0.835**	0.874**
Parental academic support	0.253**	0.320**	-	-
Communication with parents	0.190**	0.304**	0.306**	0.221**
Cronbach's alpha	0.82	0.83	0.85	0.88

Note. Pearson's r correlation coefficients are presented in the table. ** - Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. * - Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

4.2.3 Relatedness support

For assessing *relatedness support*, we used four items reflecting students' perception about the emotional supportive interaction with teachers. When teachers are sensitive, take time for students and are available in case of need, they create environment where students feel they are safe to explore and gain new experience (Skinner, Belmont, 1993). Respondents were asked to express their agreement to such support aspects as:

- Teachers support us, encourage us to trust in our own strengths;
- Teachers notice and encourage our efforts to learn;
- Teachers take the time to talk to you about how you are doing;
- Teachers tell you what you are doing well and advise you on how you can achieve better results.

Each item was assessed on a 4-point ratio scale: 1- *completely disagree*, 2- *disagree*, 3- *agree*, 4- *completely agree*. The total score for the scale is calculated by averaging the responses for four items. The mean score represents the level of student's relatedness support. Higher scores indicate higher relatedness support. The same items and identical response scale were used to assess relatedness support concept across different rounds of NSSA (2012-2016) (see table 4.2.3.1).

Descriptive statistics. Descriptives for the scale are presented in tables 4.2.3.2 and 4.2.3.3. Mean scores are between 2.8 and 3.1, when the maximum values are 4. Median scores are 3.0, indicating that half of participants indicated that their relatedness support is higher than value of 3.0.

Values of skewness are negative (between -0.59 and -0.30) across different rounds of NSSA indicating that data are a little skewed to the left side. Values of kurtosis are between 0.74 and 1.23. Overall, a normal distribution of this scale data could be assumed.

Individual differences are the main source of variance in relatedness support. Differences between schools account for 7.2% to 11.0 % of variance in relatedness support. (see ICC scores in table 4.2.3.2).

Structural validity. The unidimensional nature of the scale was supported by the findings from exploratory factor analysis (principal axis factoring) for the four relatedness support items (see table 4.2.3.4). Across all four datasets, a single factor with eigenvalue > 1 was identified. The total variance explained by the single factor ranged from 63.11 % to 69.93 %. All item loadings were above the common cut-off point of 0.40 in all datasets.

Convergent/ divergent validity. The findings indicated strong positive correlations between relatedness support and other teaching characteristics: competence support and autonomy support (between 0.78 and 0.87). From moderate to strong positive correlation are observed between relatedness support and such students characteristics as: academics self-concept, emotional school engagement and academic task value (between 0.28 and 0.58). Correlation between relatedness support and victimization in bullying are zero to weak negative (between -0.1 and -0.03). Moderate positive

correlations are observed between relatedness support and relationships with parents (between 0.2 and 0.32). Correlations between relatedness support and academic achievement are zero to weak (between -0.10 and 0.10) (see table 4.2.3.5).

Internal consistency. Acceptable internal consistency was observed for the scale across all rounds of NSSA, Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.80 to 0.86.

Table 4.2.3.1. Relatedness support: Scale structure and syntax

Intro: Do you agree with these statements:			
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
K1b/Teachers support us, encourage us to trust in our own strengths/ <i>Mokytojai palaiko mus, skatina pasitikėti savo jėgomis</i>	K1b/Teachers support us, encourage us to trust in our own strengths/ <i>Mokytojai palaiko mus, skatina pasitikėti savo jėgomis</i>	K1b/Teachers support us, encourage us to trust in our own strengths/ <i>Mokytojai palaiko mus, skatina pasitikėti savo jėgomis</i>	K1b/Teachers support us, encourage us to trust in our own strengths/ <i>Mokytojai palaiko mus, skatina pasitikėti savo jėgomis</i>
K1c/Teachers notice and encourage our efforts to learn/ <i>Mokytojai pastebi ir paskatina mūsų pastangas mokytis</i>	K1c/Teachers notice and encourage our efforts to learn/ <i>Mokytojai pastebi ir paskatina mūsų pastangas mokytis</i>	K1c/Teachers notice and encourage our efforts to learn/ <i>Mokytojai pastebi ir paskatina mūsų pastangas mokytis</i>	K1c/Teachers notice and encourage our efforts to learn/ <i>Mokytojai pastebi ir paskatina mūsų pastangas mokytis</i>
K6c/Teachers take the time to talk to you about how you are doing/ <i>Mokytojai skiria laiko pasikalbėti su Tavimi apie tai, kaip Tau sekasi mokytis</i>	K6c/Teachers take the time to talk to you about how you are doing/ <i>Mokytojai skiria laiko pasikalbėti su Tavimi apie tai, kaip Tau sekasi mokytis</i>	K6c/Teachers take the time to talk to you about how you are doing/ <i>Mokytojai skiria laiko pasikalbėti su Tavimi apie tai, kaip Tau sekasi mokytis</i>	K6c/Teachers take the time to talk to you about how you are doing/ <i>Mokytojai skiria laiko pasikalbėti su Tavimi apie tai, kaip Tau sekasi mokytis</i>
K6b/Teachers tell you what you are doing well and advise you on how you can achieve better results/ <i>Mokytojai pasako Tau, ką atlieki gerai, ir pataria, kaip galėtum pasiekti geresnių rezultatų</i>	K6b/Teachers tell you what you are doing well and advise you on how you can achieve better results/ <i>Mokytojai pasako Tau, ką atlieki gerai, ir pataria, kaip galėtum pasiekti geresnių rezultatų</i>	K6b/Teachers tell you what you are doing well and advise you on how you can achieve better results/ <i>Mokytojai pasako Tau, ką atlieki gerai, ir pataria, kaip galėtum pasiekti geresnių rezultatų</i>	K6b/Teachers tell you what you are doing well and advise you on how you can achieve better results/ <i>Mokytojai pasako Tau, ką atlieki gerai, ir pataria, kaip galėtum pasiekti geresnių rezultatų</i>
Response scale:		<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Completely disagree</i> 2. <i>Disagree</i> 3. <i>Agree</i> 4. <i>Completely agree</i> 	

Intro: Do you agree with these statements:

2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
		Missings: 98, 99	

Scale total

ReSUPP=MEAN(K1b, K1c, K6a, K6b) ReSUPP=MEAN(K1b, K1c, K6a, K6b) ReSUPP=MEAN(K1b, K1c, K6a, K6b) ReSUPP=MEAN(K1b, K1c, K6a, K6b)

Table 4.2.3.2. Relatedness support: Scale descriptives

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	988	827	426	430
Missing	3491	2936	3056	2280
Min - Max	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4
Mean (SD)	2.84 (0.57)	2.80 (0.57)	2.93 (0.57)	3.14 (0.59)
Median	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Skewness (st.error)	-0.30 (0.08)	-0.42 (0.09)	-0.36 (0.19)	-0.59 (0.12)
Kurtosis (st.error)	0.74 (0.16)	1.15 (0.17)	1.04 (0.24)	1.23 (0.24)
ICC (school)	0.107	0.072*	0.110	0.078

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in relatedness support accounted by school-level differences.

Table 4.2.3.3. Relatedness support: Histograms

Table 4.2.3.4. Relatedness support: Factor structure

	Results of exploratory factor analysis			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
No of factors with eigenvalue >1	1	1	1	1
Total variance explained by factor 10. %	63.11	63.78	62.94	69.93
No of items for factor 1	4	4	4	4
Mix – max factor loadings	0.60 - 0.81	0.61 - 0.81	0.63 - 0.77	0.71 - 0.85

Note. Principal axis factoring is applied to evaluate factor structure of a scale.

Table 4.2.3.5. Relatedness support: Construct validity and internal consistency

Correlates	Relatedness support			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
Mathematics achievement	-0.059	-0.055	-0.031	0.098*
Reading achievement	-0.091**	-0.100*	-0.041	0.015
Academic value	0.280**	0.375**	0.334**	0.570**
Academic self-concept	0.296**	0.430**	0.405**	0.583**

Emotional engagement	0.328**	0.394**	0.418**	0.368**
Victimization in bullying	-0.081*	-0.134**	-0.109*	-0.204**
Autonomy support	0.771**	0.801**	0.806**	0.835**
Competence support	0.817**	0.820**	0.835**	0.874**
Parental academic support	0.235**	0.318**	-	-
Communication with parents	0.200**	0.276**	0.324**	0.264**
Cronbach's alpha	0.80	0.81	0.80	0.86

Note. Pearson's r correlation coefficients are presented in the table. ** - Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level. * - Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level.

5. ASSESSING RELATIONSHIPS WITH PARENTS

5.1 Parental academic support

5.1.1 Theoretical conceptualization of the construct

Parental academic support is a complex construct associated with student success (Shukla et al. 2015, Rogers et al. 2018, McNeal, 1999). Parental academic support can be classified and defined in terms of *home-based* or *school-based parental involvement* (Jeynes, 2010, Bakker et al. 2007), *direct behaviours* (e.g. supervision of homework), and *emotional tone* or *supportive and encouraging parental involvement* (Rogers et al. 2018). Jeynes (2010) revealed that home-based parental involvement is more important for school success than parental school-based involvement.

Parental supportive and encouraging involvement or *autonomy support* has its basis in self-determination theory and has been defined as parental behaviors that promote choice versus parental controlling/pressuring behaviors (Shukla et al. 2015). Parental autonomy support (behaviors that promote choice) which manifests itself as parents' active interest in students' daily and long-term educational activities can take different forms, such as family routine, parental aspirations, parental cognitive stimulation (Shukla et al. 2015), parent-child discussion, educational support strategies (McNeal, 1999).

In adolescence, parental autonomy support is associated with better school outcomes in children (Simpkins et al. 2006) and positively impacts children's achievement by improving both skill development and the child's intrinsic motivation for learning, while controlling or punitive involvement can undermine an adolescent's sense of competence and autonomy and lead to decreased motivation to learn (Rogers et al. 2018).

Active parent-child communication, expression of parental expectations for education, fostering educational and occupational aspirations, discussing learning strategies conveys to children the importance of schooling and education, strengthens self-regulated learning. Conversations and questioning reveal problems still in the beginning, prevent nonnormative behavior, school truancy and dropping out (Shukla et al. 2015, McNeal, 1999, Jeynes, 2007).

Parent involvement is more effective for higher-SES students. In other words, while parent-child discussion is generally effective at reducing the likelihood of truancy and dropping out and occasionally at raising levels of science achievement, it tends to be much less effective for members of the lower socio-economic status. In many circumstances, once a student is one standard deviation below the mean on SES, the positive benefits of parent involvement disappear. This is explained by the fact that higher-SES parents are well acquainted with the jargon of education systems and have more positive personal experiences with schooling (McNeal, 1999).

5.1.2 Operationalization of the construct in NSSA data

The operationalization of parental academic support in NSSA data is in line with the conceptualization of the phenomenon as a unidimensional construct covering several forms of parental academic support, including parents' interest in how child is doing in school, their active encouragement of a child using verbal and non-verbal rewards, and provision of assistance for child during learning. The scale used to assess the level of parental academic support for students asking about the frequency of the three activities and about the agreement for one statement:

How often are parents interested in your learning?

- Ask how you fared at school;
- Praise, encourage, advise;
- Reward for good learning.

Do you agree with these statements about your family, home?

- You have someone to turn to for help with learning when you need it.

Frequency of activities was assessed on a 4-point ratio scale: 1- *never*, 2 *sometimes*, 3- *often*, 4-*very often*. Notably, the measure does not specify a period of reference for reporting parents activities. Agreement for the statement was assessed on a 4-point ratio scale: 1- *completely disagree*, 2- *disagree*, 3- *agree*, 4- *completely agree*.

The total score for the scale is calculated by averaging the responses for all four items. The mean score represents the level of student's perceived parental academic support. Higher scores indicate perceived higher parental academic support. The same items and identical response scale were used to assess parental academic support across two rounds of NSSA (2012 and 2014) (see table 5.1.1).

5.1.3 Descriptive statistics

Descriptives for the scale are presented in tables 5.1.2 and 5.1.3. Mean scores are close to value of 3, when the maximum values are 4. Median scores are also close to value of 3, indicating that half of the participants reported that their parental academic support is higher than the value of 3.

Values of skewness and kurtosis are negative indicating that data are a little skewed to the left side. However, values of skewness and kurtosis are between -0.5 and 0.5 indicating that distributions of parental academic support scale are fairly symmetric and a normal distribution of data could be assumed.

Individual differences are the main source of variance in parental academic support. Differences between schools account for 2.9% (in year 2012) and 4.4 % (in year 2014) of variance in parental academic support (see ICC scores in table 5.1.2).

5.1.4 Scale validity in NSSA data

Structural validity. The unidimensional nature of the scale was supported by the findings from exploratory factor analysis (principal axis factoring) for the four parental academic support items (see table 5.1.4). Across two datasets, a single factor with

eigenvalue > 1 was identified. The total variance explained by the single factor is 37.67% in 2012 dataset and 41% in 2014 dataset. All item loadings were above the common cut-off point of 0.40 in both datasets.

Convergent/ divergent validity. Moderate positive correlations are observed between parental academic support and such students characteristics as: academics self-concept, emotional school engagement and academic task value (between 0.22 and 0.38). Correlation between parental academic support and victimization in bullying are weak negative (~ -0.15). Strong positive correlations are observed between parental academic support and communication with parents (~ 0.60). Weak positive correlations (between 0.08 and 0.12) are observed between parental academic support and academic achievement (see table 5.1.5).

Internal consistency. Acceptable internal consistency was observed for the scale across two rounds of NSSA, Cronbach's alpha was 0.69 for 2012 dataset and 0.71 for 2014 dataset.

Table 5.1.1. Parental academic support: Scale structure and syntax

Intro: How often are parents interested in your learning? (for B19a, B19b, B19c); Do you agree with these statements about your family, home? (for B18d)

2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
B19a/ Ask how you fared at school [<i>Paklausia, kaip Tau sekėsi mokykloje</i>]	B19a/ Ask how you fared at school [<i>Paklausia, kaip Tau sekėsi mokykloje</i>]	-	-
B19b/ Praise, encourage, advise [<i>Pagiria, padrąsina, pataria</i>]	B19b/ Praise, encourage, advise [<i>Pagiria, padrąsina, pataria</i>]	-	-
B19c/ Reward for good learning [<i>Kuo nors apdovanoja už gerą mokymąsi</i>]	B19c/ Reward for good learning [<i>Kuo nors apdovanoja už gerą mokymąsi</i>]	-	-
B18d/ You have someone to turn to for help with learning when you need it[<i>Tu turi į ką kreiptis pagalbos mokantis, kai jos reikia</i>]	B18d/ You have someone to turn to for help with learning when you need it[<i>Tu turi į ką kreiptis pagalbos mokantis, kai jos reikia</i>]	-	-
Response scale (for B19a, B19b, B19c):		1- <i>Never</i> 2- <i>Sometimes</i> 3- <i>Often</i> 4- <i>Very often</i>	
Response scale (for B18d):		1. <i>Completely disagree</i> 2. <i>Disagree</i> 3. <i>Agree</i> 4. <i>Completely agree</i>	
Missings:		98, 99	

Scale total

Intro: How often are parents interested in your learning? (for B19a, B19b, B19c); Do you agree with these statements about your family, home? (for B18d)

2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
P_ACSUP = MEAN(B19a, B19b, B19c, B18d)	P_ACSUP = MEAN(B19a, B19b, B19c, B18d)	-	-

Table 5.1.2. Parental academic support: Scale descriptives

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	4468	3756	-	-
Missing	11	7	-	-
Min - Max	1 - 4	1 - 4	-	-
Mean (SD)	2.92 (0.56)	2.95 (0.58)	-	-
Median	3.00	3.00	-	-
Skewness (st.error)	-0.26 (0.04)	-0.23 (0.04)	-	-
Kurtosis (st.error)	-0.12 (0.07)	-0.21 (0.08)	-	-
ICC (school)	0.029	0.044	-	-

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in parents’ academic support accounted by school-level differences.

Table 5.1.3. Parental academic support: Histograms

Table 5.1.4. Parental academic support: Factor structure

	Results of exploratory factor analysis			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
No of factors with eigenvalue >1	1	1	-	-
Total variance explained by factor 10. %	37.67	41.00	-	-
No of items for factor 1	4	4	-	-
Mix – max factor loadings	0.45 - 0.84	0.47 - 0.84	-	-

Note. Principal axis factoring is applied to evaluate factor structure of a scale.

Table 5.1.5. Parental academic support: Construct validity and internal consistency

Correlates	Parents' academic support			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
Mathematics achievement	0.100**	0.082**	-	-
Reading achievement	0.077**	0.124**	-	-
Academic value	0.223**	0.378**	-	-
Academic self-concept	0.261**	0.366**	-	-
Emotional engagement	0.276**	0.291**	-	-
Victimization in bullying	-0.145**	-0.150**	-	-
Autonomy support	0.202**	0.290**	-	-
Competence support	0.253**	0.320**	-	-
Relatedness support	0.235**	0.318**	-	-
Communication with parents	0.559**	0.596**	-	-
Cronbach's alpha	0.69	0.71	-	-

Note. Pearson's r correlation coefficients are presented in the table. All correlations are significant at the .001 level

5.2 Communication with parents

5.2.1 Theoretical conceptualization of the construct

The family communication patterns theory emphasizes the creation of a shared social reality as a fundamental principle of family functioning. Sharing social reality facilitates understanding and comprehension, which increases efficiency and coordination and reduces misunderstandings and conflicts. Research shows that parent-adolescent communication in the family, especially in socioeconomically disadvantaged families, plays an important role in developing the psychosocial adjustment of adolescents and young adults (Rueter & Koerner, 2008; Steinberg, 2001). Studies of parent-child communication have shown that parent-child interactions, characterized by open communication, warm and supportive behavior, and strong, consistent fulfillment of developmental expectations, have a positive effect on a child's adaptation (Rueter & Koerner, 2008).

In families where communication is open, with little conflict and relatively democratic control, teens are more likely to develop their own positive concepts that will help them better understand the world and address its challenges and problems (Lanz et al. 1999). Research has identified open parent-child communication as a protective factor, whereas problematic communication between parents and children as a risk factor for adolescent psychosocial adjustment. Some studies revealed that depressed adolescents report less communication, less exchange of thoughts and feelings with their parents, and less family cohesion than adolescents without depression. Open communication between parents and children was significantly and positively associated with the development of adolescents' moral reasoning, academic achievement, and self-esteem. Open communication can show better parent-child relationships, which can be a protective factor for children from the development of depression and anxiety and antisocial activities (Xiao et al. 2011).

5.2.2 Operationalization of the construct in NSSA data

The operationalization of communication with parents in NSSA data is in line with the conceptualization of the phenomenon as a unidimensional construct covering such aspect of communication as enjoyment, involvement and extent. Respondents were asked to express their agreement to such communications aspects as:

- You like to spend time with your family;
- You are involved in decisions (eg where to vacation together, etc.);
- Communicate with you a lot.

Each item was assessed on a 4-point ratio scale: 1- *completely disagree*, 2- *disagree*, 3- *agree*, 4- *completely agree*. The total score for the scale is calculated by averaging the responses for three items. The mean score represents the level of student's communication with parents. Higher scores indicate higher communication with parents. The same items and identical response scale were used to assess communication with parents' concept across different rounds of NSSA (2012-2016) (see table 5.2.1).

5.2.3 Descriptive statistics

Descriptives for the scale are presented in tables 5.2.2 and 5.2.3. Mean scores are between 3.1 and 3.3, when the maximum values are 4. Median scores are between 3 and 3.3, indicating that half of participants indicated that their communication with parents is higher than value of 3.

Values of skewness are negative (between -0.93 and -0.53) across different rounds of NSSA indicating that data are skewed to the left side. Values of kurtosis are between 0.82 and 1.30. Overall, a normal distribution of this scale data could be assumed.

Individual differences are the main source of variance in communication with parents. Differences between schools account for only 1.7% to 3.1 % of variance in communication with parents (see ICC scores in table 5.2.2).

5.2.4 Scale validity in NSSA data

Structural validity. The unidimensional nature of the scale was supported by the findings from exploratory factor analysis (principal axis factoring) for the three communication with parents' items (see table 5.2.4). Across all four datasets, a single factor with eigenvalue > 1 was identified. The total variance explained by the single factor ranged from 63.11 % to 69.93 %. All item loadings were above the common cut-off point of 0.40 in all datasets.

Convergent/ divergent validity. The findings showed moderate positive correlations between communication with parents and such students characteristics as: academic self-concept, emotional school engagement and academic task value (between 0.23 and 0.38). Correlation between communication with parents and victimization in bullying are weak negative (between -0.18 and -0.14). Strong positive correlations are between communication with parents and parental academic support (~ 0.60). Correlations between communication with parents and academic achievement are weak positive – between 0.06 and 0.16 (see table 5.1.4) (see table 5.2.5).

Internal consistency. Acceptable internal consistency was observed for the scale across all rounds of NSSA, Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.60 to 0.65.

Table 5.2.1. Relationship with parents: Scale structure and syntax

Intro: Do you agree with these statements about your family, home? (for the 1 st and 2 nd); Your parents/guardians (for the 3 rd)			
2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
B18a/ You like to spend time with your family <i>[Tau patinka leisti laiką kartu su namiškiais]</i>	B18a/ You like to spend time with your family <i>[Tau patinka leisti laiką kartu su namiškiais]</i>	B16a/ You like to spend time with your family <i>[Tau patinka leisti laiką kartu su namiškiais]</i>	B15a/ You like to spend time with your family <i>[Tau patinka leisti laiką kartu su namiškiais]</i>
B18c/ You are involved in decisions (eg where to vacation together, etc.) <i>[Tu dalyvauji priimant sprendimus (pvz., kur atostogauti kartu ar pan.)]</i>	B18c/ You are involved in decisions (eg where to vacation together, etc.) <i>[Tu dalyvauji priimant sprendimus (pvz., kur atostogauti kartu ar pan.)]</i>	B16c/ You are involved in decisions (eg where to vacation together, etc.) <i>[Tu dalyvauji priimant sprendimus (pvz., kur atostogauti kartu ar pan.)]</i>	B15c/ You are involved in decisions (eg where to vacation together, etc.) <i>[Tu dalyvauji priimant sprendimus (pvz., kur atostogauti kartu ar pan.)]</i>
B16b/ Communicate with you a lot <i>[su Tavimi daug bendrauja]</i>	B16b/ Communicate with you a lot <i>[su Tavimi daug bendrauja]</i>	B13b/ Communicate with you a lot <i>[su Tavimi daug bendrauja]</i>	B12b/ Communicate with you a lot <i>[su Tavimi daug bendrauja]</i>
		Response scale:	1. <i>Completely disagree</i> 2. <i>Disagree</i> 3. <i>Agree</i> 4. <i>Completely agree</i>
		Missings:	98, 99
Scale total			
P_REL = MEAN(B18a, B18c, B16b)	P_REL = MEAN(B18a, B18c, B16b)	P_REL = MEAN(B16a, B16c, B13b)	P_REL = MEAN(B15a, B15c, B12b)

Table 5.2.2. Relationship with parents: Scale descriptives

	2012 (8th grade)	2014 (8th grade)	2015 (8th grade)	2016 (6th grade)
N	4463	3757	3452	2701
Missing	16	6	30	9
Min - Max	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4	1 - 4
Mean (SD)	3.07 (0.54)	3.09 (0.56)	3.2 (0.55)	3.32 (0.56)
Median	3.0	3.0	3.33	3.33
Skewness (st.error)	-0.53 (0.04)	-0.60 (0.04)	-0.7 (0.04)	-0.93 (0.05)
Kurtosis (st.error)	0.82 (0.07)	1.08 (0.08)	0.91 (0.08)	1.3 (0.09)
ICC (school)	0.018	0.031	0.017	0.020

Note. ICC (school) – intra-class correlation coefficient, indicating a share of variance in relationship with parents accounted by school-level differences.

Table 5.2.3. Relationship with parents: Histograms

Table 5.2.4. Relationship with parents: Factor structure

	Results of exploratory factor analysis			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
No of factors with eigenvalue >1	1	1	1	1
Total variance explained by factor 10. %	36.56	40.05	35.0	33.8
No of items for factor 1	3	3	3	3
Mix – max factor loadings	0.49 - 0.69	0.53 - 0.74	0.51 - 0.71	0.53 - 0.62

Note. Principal axis factoring is applied to evaluate factor structure of a scale.

Table 5.2.5. Relationship with parents: Construct validity and internal consistency

Correlates	Relationship with parents			
	2012	2014	2015	2016
Mathematics achievement	0.057**	0.093**	0.061	0.072**
Reading achievement	0.101**	0.131**	0.163**	0.133**
Academic value	0.234**	0.377**	0.301**	0.265**
Academic self-concept	0.273**	0.337**	0.286**	0.288**
Emotional engagement	0.302**	0.303**	0.311**	0.324**
Victimization in bullying	-0.138**	-0.182**	-0.182**	-0.165**
Autonomy support	0.170**	0.243**	0.323**	0.214**
Competence support	0.190**	0.304**	0.306**	0.221**
Relatedness support	0.200**	0.276**	0.324**	0.264**
Parental academic support	0.559**	0.596**	-	-
Cronbach's alpha	0.62	0.65	0.60	0.60

Note. Pearson's r correlation coefficients are presented in the table. All correlations are significant at .001. ** - Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

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